

ICAENS 2022 PROGRAM

Session 1.1		10 NOVEMBER 2022 10:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-1	Katmanlı imalat ile yüksek sıcaklık dayanımlı polimerik malzemeden kalıp imalatı ve hızlı prototip üretimi	Gökşan Şan	Turkey	Submission 44
O-2	Post-impact compressive strength of carbon/epoxy laminates toughened with non-woven thermoplastic veils	Mehmet Çağatay Akbolat, Kali Babu Katnam and Prasad Potluri	UK, UK, UK	Submission 333
O-3	Low-velocity Impact Response of Interlaminar Toughened Composite Laminates	Mehmet Çağatay Akbolat, Kali Babu Katnam and Prasad Potluri	UK, UK, UK	Submission 334
O-4	Biyomimekri ile form ve yüzey oluşturma: otomotiv uygulamasına yönelik bir örnek	Gökşan Şan	Turkey	Submission 43

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-5	Synthesis and Photoelectrocatalytic Characterization of Anodic TiO ₂ Electrode for Orange G Degradation	Berrak ÇALIŞKAN, Enes ŞAYAN, Hakan KIZILTAŞ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 399
O-6	COMPARISON OF QUALITY CHARACTERISTICS OF CONVENTIONALLY AND MICROWAVE-ASSISTED CONVENTIONALLY BAKED CRACKERS	Duygu Başkaya Sezer	Turkey	Submission 230
O-7	Investigation of tensile and delamination behavior of carbon fiber epoxy composites reinforced with different weight ratio graphene oxide nanoparticles	Tahir Soyugüzel, Zahit Mecitoğlu, Hülya Kaftelen-Odabaşı	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 250
O-8	EFFECTS OF CITRIC ACID AND BORIC ACID ON VISCOSITY AND BOND STRENGTH OF GUAR GUM ADHESIVE	Mehmet Emin Ergun	Turkey	Submission 311

Session 1.3		10 NOVEMBER 2022 11:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-9	Sustainable Organic Matter Management in Turkey	Asuman Büyükkılıç Yanardağ and İbrahim Halil Yanardağ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 162
O-10	Barriers Affecting Resilience in the Food Supply Chain During the Covid-19 Pandemic Period	Nimet Nur Güneş, Ahmet Çalık	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 198
O-11				
O-12	A New MCDM Framework for Pharmaceutical Product Marketing in the COVID-19 Era	Nur Atik, Ahmet Çalık	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 288

Session 1.4		10 NOVEMBER 2022 11:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-13	Discretization, Stability And Bifurcation Analysis Caputo-Fabrizio Logistic Model With Additive Allee Effect	Hatice Karakaya, Şenol Kartal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 47
O-14	CNN BASED REAL TIME SYSTEM DESIGN AND CLASSIFICATION OF RECYCLABLE WASTE	İbrahim ÖZKAL, Fatih Başçiftçi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 29
O-15	Multi Objective Optimization with Regression Methods for the High Voltage Cable Bonding	BAHADIR AKBAL	Turkey	Submission 254
O-16	Blozkinciri Tabanlı Kimlik Doğrulama Yöntemleri ve Uygulama Önerileri	Mustafa TANRIVERDİ, Mevlüt UYSAL, Onur CERAN, Mutlu Tahsin ÜSTÜNDAĞ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 277

Session 1.5		10 NOVEMBER 2022 13:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-17	Uçucu Külün Puzolan Olarak Kullanıldığı Kendiliğinden Yerleşen Betonlarda Basınç Dayanımının Zamana Bağlı İncelenmesi	Fethi İŞSEVER, Sadık VAROL GÜNEŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 397
O-18	Yüksek Oranlarda Uçucu Kül Kullanımının Kendiliğinden Yerleşen Betonlarda İleri Yaşlar İçin Eğilmede Çekme Dayanımının Araştırılması	Fethi İŞSEVER	Turkey	Submission 398
O-19	PLANT-DERIVED EXOSOME-LIKE NANOPARTICLES: A RESEARCH ON ITS EXTRACTION METHODS AND EFFECTS ON CANCER	Ayşegül DEMİRHAN, Semra TÜRKOĞLU, Fazilet ERMAN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 110
O-20	MALZEMENİN MEKANİK VE METALOGRAFİK ÖZELLİKLERİNİN GELİŞTİRİLMESİNDE DÜŞÜK BASINÇLI SEMENTASYON YÖNTEMİNİN ÜSTÜNLÜKLERİ	Şerife HELVACIOĞLU, Ümmihan T. YILMAZ, Ayşe ERKAN and Çelebi ERSOY	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 17

Session 1.6		10 NOVEMBER 2022 13:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-21	Blow up of positive initial energysolutions for variable coefficients wave equation	Ayşe Fidan and Erhan Pişkin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 339
O-22	Nonexistence of global solutions for variable coefficients wave equationwith negative initial energy	Ayşe Fidan and Erhan Pişkin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 340
O-23	Finite time blow up of solutions for variable exponent parabolic type equation	Gülistan Butakın and Erhan Pişkin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 297
O-24	Exponential growth of solutions for variable exponent parabolic type equation	Gülistan Butakın and Erhan Pişkin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 298

Session 1.7		10 NOVEMBER 2022 14:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-25	Exergy Analysis of Inlet Air Absorption Cooling Effects on Basic Cogeneration Systems	Rabi KARAALİ, Arzu KEVEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 131
O-26	Performance Analysis of Air Fuel Heating Effects on Cogeneration Cycles	Rabi KARAALİ, Arzu KEVEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 134
O-27	Application of the Ohmic Heating Process to Make a Milk Semolina Dessert	Hatice Pinar Yuksel, Serdal Sabanci and Basri Omac	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 482
O-28	Modelling and Analysis of Gyroscopic Effects in Rotating Systems	Abdülşamet Erkan, Hasan Körük and Kenan Y. Şanlıtürk	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 688

Session 1.8		10 NOVEMBER 2022 14:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-29	Oflak Dağı (Sakarya) Amerobelboid akar (Acari: Oribatida) Faunası Üzerine Sistematik Çalışmalar	Şahin YELEK, Şule BARAN, Diğdem YELEK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 300
O-30	Kasatura Körfezi Tabiatı Koruma Alanı Ciğerotları (Marchantiophyta) Florası	Özcan ŞİMŞEK and Yasin ÜNAL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 444
O-31	Economical And Efficient Ways To Run An Ecological-Friendly Dairy Business	Zohaib Sultan, Mahmood Ul Hassan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 559
O-32	Impact of Humic Acid Application on Yield and Quality Characteristics of Some Salvia Species	Buse Şefika AYDIN, Tuba ARJUMEND, Mehmet Uğur YILDIRIM, Ercüment Osman SARIHAN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 803

Session 1.9		10 NOVEMBER 2022 15:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-33	Evaluation of Electricity Generation Potential of Fruit and Vegetable Waste and Cow Manure by Biogas	Kaptan Rutkay, Topac F. Olcay	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 555
O-34	Plants and Biomimicry: Strategies for a Sustainable World	Cennet Özay	Turkey	Submission 557
O-35	Hydrological Drought Analysis by Streamflow Drought Index and Innovative Trend Analysis: A Case Study of Kızılırmak Basin of Turkey	Ibrahim Halil DEGER, Mehmet Ishak YUCE and Musa ESIT	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 589
O-36	Acari of Myotis emerginatus and Minopterus schreibersii (Vespertilionidae) collected from Bursa Province, of Türkiye	Nurhan SÜMER, Muhlis ÖZKAN and Hikmet Sami YILDIRIMHAN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 495

Session 1.10		10 NOVEMBER 2022 15:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-37	HEMŞİRELİK ÖĞRENCİLERİNİN KLİNİK UYGULAMALARA YÖNELİK TUTUMLARININ BELİRLENMESİ	Nihal TAŞKIRAN, Güleğün TÜRK, Orhan ER	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 419
O-38	Hemşirelerin Hemşirelik Süreci Uygulamasına İlişkin Yaşadıkları Güçlükler: Sistematik İnceleme	Nihal TAŞKIRAN, Güleğün TÜRK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 421
O-39	İndolamin-2,3-dioksijenaz-1 inhibitörleri uygulanan triple negatif meme kanseri hücrelerinde immün kaçışta miR-34a ve miR-155'in rolünün araştırılması	Kaan Furkan HAMARAT, Şuranur AYVAZ and Gamze GÜNEY ESKİLER	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 674
O-40	Bazı Yeni Hidrazon Bileşiklerinin Sentezi ve Kolinesteraz İnhibisyon Potansiyellerinin Belirlenmesi	Ercan Çınar, Mehmet Boğa	Turkey	Submission 729

Session 1.11		10 NOVEMBER 2022 16:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-41	k-Nearest Neighbor and random forest algorithms to predict appointment compliance of patients in the chemotherapy department	Abdulkadir Atalan	Turkey	Submission 525
O-42	Circular Gudermannian Distribution and Application to Wind Direction Data	Abdullah Yılmaz	Turkey	Submission 708
O-43	Birinci mertebe bir trafik akım yaklaşımının sonlu fark esaslı çizgiler yöntemi ile sayısal modellemesi	Rabia Kılıç, Nurten Akgün-Tanbay ve Tayfun Tanbay	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 497
O-44	Elektrikli Araç Batarya Sistemleri için Yarım Köprü DC/DC Dönüştürücü Yapısıyla Bir AC/DC Anahtarlama Güç Kaynağı Tasarımı ve Uygulaması	Celaletdin Akgül, Yücel Çetinceviz and Erdal Şehirli	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 747

Session 1.12		10 NOVEMBER 2022 16:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-45	Minimal Submanifolds of Metallic Riemannian Manifolds	Mustafa Gök	Turkey	Submission 785
O-46	Pest Detection On Traps Based On Deep Learning Techniques	Gülhan Şikaroğlu, Sinan Uğuz and İsmail Karaca	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 823
O-47	Initial Matrix and Solving Methods Effect on Estimation of OD Matrix	İsmail Tengirşek, Yavuz Delice	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 867
O-48	A review on tidal energy – In the perspective of sustainability	Burçin ATILGAN TÜRKMEN	Turkey	Submission 539

Session 2.1		11 NOVEMBER 2022 09:00-10:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-1	THE EFFECT OF THE INCLUSION OF BASEMENT FLOORS IN THE ANALYTICAL MODEL ON THE SEISMIC PERFORMANCE ESTIMATION OF LOW-RISE REINFORCED CONCRETE BUILDINGS	Birkan DAĞ and Muzaffer BÖREKÇİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 38
T-2	Belirsizlik Problemlerine Yönelik Bazı Yeni Matematiksel Modeller	Orhan Dalkılıç and Naime Demirtaş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 42
T-3	RENEWABLE ENERGY AND ENERGY TARIFFS: SOLAR TARIFFS	Khandan ROSHANA EI, Edip TAŞKESEN, and Mehmet ÖZKAYMAK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 95
T-4	Bitümlü sıcak karışımlarda yarım daire eğilme deneyinin XFEM yaklaşımı ile simülasyonu	Ahmet Münir Özdemir, Bahadır Yılmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 124
T-5	Activation of PDX1 gene with different activator domains by CRISPR-dCas9	Adem KABA, Fatma AKÇAKALE KABA, Ersin AKINCI and Mehmet Fatih CENGİZ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 108
T-6	Different dCas9-Activator Complexes During Activation of the NEUROG3	Adem KABA, Fatma AKÇAKALE KABA, Ersin AKINCI and Mehmet Fatih CENGİZ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 109
T-7	A Damselfly Record, Pyrrhosoma nymphula (Sulzer, 1776) (Coenagrionidae, Odonata) in Turkey, with notes on its distribution	Ali MİROĞLU	Turkey	Submission 143
T-8	Askeri Alanda Endüstri 4.0 Uygulamaları	Güzide KARAKUŞ and İbrahim GÖNEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 128
T-9	Axial Vibration of Boron-nitride Nanotubes in Elastic Medium	Güler Gaygusuzoğlu	Turkey	Submission 167
T-10	Elastomer Mesnetli Karayolu Köprülerinin Farklı Orta Ayak Kolon Yükseklikleri İçin Deprem Davranışları	Yersaiyn BEXULTAN, Ali İhsan KARAKAŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 164

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-11	Ultra Yüksek Mukavemetli S1100 Çeliğinin MQL koşullarında Frezelenmesinin Takım Aşınması Üzerindeki Etkileri	Serhat Şap	Turkey	Submission 185
T-12	Determination of Mechanical Properties of Glass Fiber Reinforced Composites using Allen's Method	Ali İmran Ayten, Bazle Z. (Gama) Haque	Turkey, USA	Submission 187
T-13	Bi-interior Ideals of Nearness Semigroups	ÖZLEM TEKİN	Turkey	Submission 165
T-14	Bazı odun dışı orman ürünleri, sağladığı faydalar ve ülkemiz ekonomisi açısından önemi	Bekircan BALCI, Murat KÖSE	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 186
T-15	LİMAN İŞLETMELERİNDE ÖZELLEŞTİRME VE SWOT ANALİZİ	Murat YORULMAZ, Nurettin BÜYÜK	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 4
T-16	KAN VERİLERİNE GÖRE KARACİĞERDE OLUŞAN HASTALIKLARIN MAKİNE ÖĞRENMESİ METHODLARI İLE TESPİT EDİLMESİ	Cengiz Sertkaya, Sadettin Emre Yalçın	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 104
T-17	Felç Geçirme Riskinin Makine Öğrenmesi Yöntemleri ile Tahmin Edilmesi	Cengiz Sertkaya, Kardelen Kamışlı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 105
T-18	Trend analysis of monthly total precipitation data using four different methods in Rize station, Turkey	M. Kürşad ACAR, Yavuz AVSAROĞLU, Veysel GÜMÜS, Oğuz ŞİMŞEK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 252
T-19	Başlık Tavuk Karaciğeri Glutatyon S-Transferaz Enzimi Üzerine Bazı Pestisitlerin Etkileri	Hakan YILMAZ, Mehmet ÇİFTÇİ, Yusuf TEMEL	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 245
T-20	Cumulative impact of marble quarry activities on Lake Yarıslı (Yeşilova-Burdur-Turkey)	Mehmet Özçelik	Turkey	Submission 222

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-21	Thermodynamic Analysis of an Electric Water Kettle with a Phase Change Material Insulation	Murat KADAL, Hasan Alpay HEPERKAN and Kenan KAYA	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 249
T-22	Modeling and Simulation of the FOC strategy for ACIM and PMSM with Electric Vehicle	Osamah Neamah, Raif Bayir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 218
T-23	Cumulative impact of marble quarry activities on Lake Yarisli (Yeşilova-Burdur-Turkey)	Mehmet Özçelik	Turkey	Submission 222
T-24	Visualization of 3D Model Based on Photogrammetry Technique Using WebGL	Ahmet Uslu	Turkey	Submission 253
T-25	Determining turning parameters effects on Nimax mold steel cutting forces	Rüstem Binali and Mustafa Kuntoğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 246
T-26	Network-based Omics Data Integration to Identify Repurposed Drugs for Prolactinoma	Büşra AYDIN	Turkey	Submission 296
T-27	Maden Aramalarında Levenberg-Marquart Yönteminin Kullanılması	Ezgi Erbek Kıran	Turkey	Submission 336
T-28	BREEDING METHODS USED IN MEDICINAL AND AROMATIC PLANTS	Betül Gıdık	Turkey	Submission 182
T-29	Jelâtime Fonksiyonel Özellikler Kazandırma Çalışmaları İle İlgili Bir Araştırma	Abdülkadir DİLBER and Süleyman GÖKMEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 337
T-30	UAV Selection with MULTIMOORA Method: An International Comparison	Adnan Abdulvahitoğlu, Aslı Abdulvahitoğlu, Özhan BAŞBOĞA	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 325

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T-31	Critical Path Method With Fuzzy Activity Times	Özlem Çomaklı Sökmen	Turkey	mail submission 3
T-32	Process Optimization with Simulation and an Application	Özlem Çomaklı Sökmen	Turkey	Submission 177
T-33	Fuzzy Linear Programming Model For Critical Path Method: A Case Study	Özlem Çomaklı Sökmen	Turkey	Submission 178
T-34	A novel conditional connectivity measure for graphs	Süleyman Ediz	Turkey	Submission 332
T-35	Performance Evaluation of Supercritical CO2 Brayton Cycle for Low Temperature Applications	Serpil ÇELİK TOKER, Önder KIZILKAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 294
T-36	Doğu Pontidler’de Güneydere Plütonu’nun (Bayburt, KD-Türkiye) Saha Özellikleri ve Petrografik Karakteristikleri: Ön Bulgular	Mehmet Ali Gücer, Zeynep Delimehmet	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 322
T-37	BALIKESİR İLİ HAVA SICAKLIĞINI TAHMİNİ İÇİN VERİ MADENCİLİĞİ YÖNTEMLERİNİ KARŞILAŞTIRILMASI	Oğuzhan DİLBER, Serhat KILIÇARSLAN and Samet PANDA	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 247
T-38	Grouping the Number of People who Lost Lives Due to Covid-19 in OECD Countries by Clustering Analysis	Cengiz Gazeloğlu and Tunahan Turhan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 352
T-39	Employment Data Analysis for Türkiye in Covid19 Outbreak Using Grey Incidence Analysis	Erdal Aydemir, Yusuf Şahin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 326
T-40	Maleik asidin renal kanser hücre hatları üzerindeki sitotoksik ve apoptotik etkilerinin incelenmesi	Burçin İrem ABAS, Ömer ERDOĞAN and Özge ÇEVİK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 305

Session 2.5		11 NOVEMBER 2022 11:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-41	Kuersetin ve N-asetilnöraminik asit kombinasyonunun yara iyileştirici özelliklerinin in-vitro incelenmesi	Ömer ERDOĞAN, Burçin İrem ABAS and Özge ÇEVİK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 304
T-42	Kısa raf ömrüne sahip bazı meyvelerin paketlenmesinde kullanılan doğal antimikrobiyal bileşenler	Reyhan İrkin	Turkey	Submission 20
T-43	Safety assessment of ship recycling hazards in marine environment under D-S evidence FMECA approach.	Muhammet Aydın, Şükrü İlke Sezer and Emre Akyüz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 28
T-44	Evaluation of Fresh State of Color Pigment Incorporated Roller Compacted Concrete	Gökhan Çalış, Sadık Alper Yıldız and Ülkü Sultan Keskin	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 37
T-45	Assessment of lactic acid bacteria isolated from koumiss for dough leavening	Azhar Makambai kyzy, Aichurok Mazhitova, Aylin Korkut Altıntaş, Hakan Kuleşan	Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 49
T-46	Mikronize Kalsit Dolgu İlaveli Kauçuk Karışımlarının Fizikomekanik, Dinamik ve Yaşlandırma Özellikleri Üzerine Etkisinin İncelenmesi	Eda YILDIRIM, Ezgi ÇELİK GÜNEY and Ebru APAYDIN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 64
T-47	Kauçuk/Metal Yapılı Burcun Sonlu Elemanlar Analiziyle Rijitlik Tayini ve Mesh Boyutunun Analiz Sonucuna Etkisinin İncelenmesi	Hamdi BAŞARAN, Şeyma Tuğba AYRANCIOĞLU	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 66
T-48	Atık Kauçukların Yeniden Kullanımının Dinamik ve Mekanik Özellikleri Üzerine Etkisinin İncelenmesi	Eda YILDIRIM, Ezgi ÇELİK GÜNEY	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 68
T-49	Bazı Keten (Linum usitatissimum L.) Çeşitlerinin Konya Koşullarında Yağ Verimlerinin Belirlenmesi	Özlem ÖRS, Özden ÖZTÜRK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 98
T-50	Mixing rate optimization of Markov chains on strongly connected digraphs with identical holding probabilities	Onur Cihan	Turkey	Submission 106

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T-51	Molecular docking and in vitro enzyme inhibition activity of a sulfonate compound: naphthalene-2-yl 4-bromobenzenesulfonate	Ercan Bursal	Turkey	Submission 203
T-52	Investigation of natural frequencies of functionally graded beams with polynomial series solution	Muhittin Turan	Turkey	Submission 113
T-53	CS/Nano-HAP-Ag Hybrit Composite Coating on TNTZ Titanium Alloy by Hydrothermal Method and Characterizations for Biomedical Application	Oktay YİĞİT	Turkey	Submission 125
T-54	Doğrusal Programlama ile Minimum Risk Hedefleyen Borsa İstanbul Katılım Endeksi Odaklı Portföy Planlama	Yunus EROĞLU and Mehmet Alp SALTIKER	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 126
T-55	On a class of Ricci quadratic Finsler metrics	SEMAIL ULGEN, ESRA SEVİM, MEHRAN GABRANİ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 148
T-56	On Some Ricci Curvature Tensors in Finsler geometry On Some Ricci Curvature Tensors in Finsler geometry	SEMAIL ÜLGEN, ZHONGMIN SHENİ, ESRA SEVİM	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 150
T-57	On Ricci-Quadratic Finsler Metrics	SEMAIL ÜLGEN, ZHONGMIN SHENİ, ESRA SEVİM	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 152
T-58	MALZEME KARAKTERİZASYONU ÇERÇEVESİNDE SERAMİK ARKEOMETRİSİ ÇALIŞMA ADIMLARI	BÜŞRA ÖZDAŞ, MURAT BAYAZİT	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 172
T-59	Elektrokoagülasyon Yöntemiyle Sulu Çözeltiden Rhodamin-B Boyar Maddesinin Giderimi	Sermin GÜNASLAN, Baybars Ali FİL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 190
T-60	Anti-Tyrosinase, Anti-Pancreatic Lipase and Anti-Acetylcholinesterase Activity Studies of 1,2,3-Triazole Compounds	Serap Kızılkaya, Ercan Bursal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 194

Session 2.7		11 NOVEMBER 2022 12:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-61	Halk Saęlıęı Açısından Et Ve Et Ürünlerindeki Mikrobiyolojik Tehlikeler	Rabia EROęLU, Nesrin ÇAKICI	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 477
T-62	USING DEEP LEARNING - BASED LSTM TO PREDICT THE STATE OF HEALTH OF LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES	Mehmet Buęra KOT, Elif KOZAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 236
T-63	OTOMOTİV ENDÜSTİRİŞİ SAC ŞEKİLLENDİRME İŞLEMİNDE ENDÜSTRİ 4.0 VE KESTİRİMCİ BAKIM YÖNTEMLERİ	Sadettin ATAĞ, Eren Can NİSAN ve M. İhsan Karamangil	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 243
T-64	Chemical Composition of Lemon and Grapefruit Pruning Residues	Koray Başol, İlhami Emrah Dönmez	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 279
T-65	A brief investigation on the abrasion resistance of porous concrete pavement	Muhammed TANYILDIZI	Turkey	Submission 280
T-66	An investigation on the use of waste materials in bitumen modification	Muhammed TANYILDIZI	Turkey	Submission 281
T-67	The Advantages of Roller Compacted Concrete Pavement	Muhammed TANYILDIZI	Turkey	Submission 282
T-68	Application of Irradiation Technology in Processed Seafood	Özen Yusuf ÖĞRETMEN	Turkey	mail submission 6
T-69	Bursa ili için evsel katı atıkta sıfır atık uygulanabilirlięi: bir anket çalışması	Nour Aljbili, Samet Öztürk	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 287
T-70	Blood Glucose Prediction from Nondiabetic and Diabetic Exhaled Breath via Machine Learning	Taleh Binnatov, Tamila Anutgan and Hakan Yılmaz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 264

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-71	FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF CENTRAL CROSSED STEEL STRUCTURE ACCORDING TO TBDY 2018 REGULATION	Hakan AYDIN	Turkey	Submission 289
T-72	Economic Analysis and Determination of Profitability of an Automotive Company's Building Construction Investment	Enes Yuvalı, Halil İbrahim Demir, Abdullah Hulusi Kökçam, and Caner Erden	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 293
T-73	Analysis of a Transcritical CO2 Rankine Cycle Integrated with Ultra-Low Temperature Refrigeration Assisted by Geothermal Energy	Serpil ÇELİK TOKER, Önder KIZILKAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 295
T-74	The effect of pixel-based classification methods to determine the impervious surface areas on pan-sharpened satellite imagery	Mustafa Hayri KESİKOĞLU	Turkey	Submission 324
T-75	Elastomer Mesnetli Karayolu Köprülerinin Farklı Orta Ayak Kolon Yükseklikleri İçin Deprem Davranışları	Yersaiyn BEXULTAN, Ali İhsan KARAKAŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 164
T-76	Passive detection of Sensor type and its location according to game theory	Tarık TUFAN	Turkey	Submission 207
T-77	Yangın ve Yüksek Sıcaklığın Betonarme Yapılardaki Beton ve Donatı Özelliklerine Etkisi	Ahmet Ferdi Şenol and Özlem Çalışkan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 349
T-78	Grouping the Number of People who Lost Lives Due to Covid-19 in OECD Countries by Clustering Analysis	Cengiz Gazeloğlu and Tunahan Turhan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 352
T-79	PATULİN MİKOTOKSİN SAĞLIK ÜZERİNE ETKİLERİ	Seydi Yıkılmış, Melike İmre, Elif Demir, Melikenur Türkol	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 355
T-80	Amplifying Training Mechanism of Elman Recurrent Neural Network: Basics and Applications	Eslam Mohammed Abdelkader, Nehal Elshaboury, Umut Özkaya	Egypt, Egypt, Turkey	Submission 361

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-81	SESLİ VE GÖRSEL UYARANLI YÜRÜME PLATFORMU- STEP ON IT	Büşra Candırı, Yunus Candırı, Burcu Talu, İbrahim Işık, Betül Yapalıkan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 373
T-82	Aras Havzası Meteorolojik Kuraklığının Değerlendirilmesi:Doğu Beyazıt İstasyonu Örneği	Elif Miraç Uncu, Oğuz Şimşek, Nazire Göksu Soydan Oksal and Veysel Gümüş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 374
T-83	Araç soğutma sistemlerindeki erkek konektörlerin metal yerine polimer kompozit kullanılarak tasarlanması	Hikmet Ulaş	Turkey	Submission 394
T-84	A multielectrochromic copolymer based on pyrrole and 3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene	Buket Bezgin Çarbaş	Turkey	Submission 403
T-85	Experimental Difficulties And Solutions In Reinforced Concrete Shear Walls	Cansu ERGİN, Fatih ALTUN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 408
T-86	Applicability of the vinyltrimethoxysilane modified diatomite for treatment of aqueous solution containing Cu(II)	Eda Gokırmak Sogut, Necla Çalışkan Kılıç	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 410
T-87	TIG ve MIG Kaynağı ile Birleştirilen AA 6061 ve AA 7075 Alaşımlarının Mikroyapı ve Mekanik İncelemeleri	Anıl İmak, İhsan Kırık	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 411
T-88	Akıllı Evler için Öznitelik Seçimi Temelli Uzun-Kısa Süreli Bellek Ağı Kullanarak Enerji Tüketim Tahmini	Birce Dağkurs, İsmail Atacak	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 412
T-89	Determination of Glaucoma Disease with Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix Features	Evin ŞAHİN SADIK	Turkey	Submission 137
T-90	MERMER TOZU VE MANYETİZE SU KULLANILARAK ÜRETİLMİŞ ÇEVRE DOSTU ÇİMENTO BAĞLAYICI KOMPOZİTLERİN DAYANIM VE DAYANIKLILIK ÖZELLİKLERİNİN İNCELENMESİ	Özer SEVİM and Ziya ŞENBAYIR	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 643

Session 2.10		11 NOVEMBER 2022 14:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-49	Photodynamic Properties of Coumarin 30 in AOT Reverse Micelles	Tuğba BAYRAKTUTAN, Yavuz ONGANER	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 19
O-50	Synthesis of Artemisinin-Pyrazole Derivatives	Güngör LÖKOĞLU, Ömrüye ÖZOK ARICI and Arif KIVRAK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 396
O-51	Investigation of Two Dimensional Tungsten Disulfide as a Buffer Layer for Solar Cells	Büşra AYDIN, Çağlar DUMAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 486
O-52	Structure Solution and Hirshfeld Surface Analysis for 6-Phenyl-keto-tetrahydropyridazine	Necmi Dege and Sevgi Kansız	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 233

Session 2.11		11 NOVEMBER 2022 13:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-91	CPM/PERT Technique Solution of Fuel Oil Power Plant Installation Project in the Caribbean Islands	Fatih Erbahar, Halil İbrahim Demir, Rakesh Kumar Phanden, Abdullah Hulusi Kökcam	Turkey, Turkey, India, Turkey	Submission 291
T-92	The Transition to 5G Project In The Telecommunications Industry Using CPM and PERT Techniques	Faruk Arslan, Halil İbrahim Demir, Caner Erden, and Burak Erkeyman	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 292
T-93	Theoretical Calculation of Lennard-Jones (12–6–4) Intermolecular Interaction Energy for TSPP	Elif Somuncu, Bahtiyar A. Mamedov	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 347
T-94	A Forecasting Method Based on Artificial Neural Networks to Estimate the Ecological Footprint in Turkey	Sevim Gülin Demirbay, Selim Gündüz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 343
T-95	Dose Assessments of NORM in Construction Materials	Ahmet Erdal OSMANLIOĞLU	Turkey	Submission 358
T-96	Klinik kararda biyokimyasal parametrelerin önemi ve hastalıklarla ilişkileri	Çağan ÇATAK, Ercan Bursal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 364
T-97	Bitkisel Tasarımlarda Dört Mevsim Renkli Bahçeler, Isparta Örneği	Şirin Dönmez and Mahmut Tuğluer	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 384
T-98	The Prasinite Mineralogy and Geochemical Properties	Ayşe Didem Kılıç, Ahmet Bingöl	Turkey	Submission 395
T-99	CIGS/CdS solar cell modelling with SCAPS-1D software	Serap Yiğit Gezgin, Yasemin Gündoğdu and Hamdi Şükür Kılıç	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 402
T-100	On The Generalized Fibonacci Matrix Hybrinomials	Sure KÖME and Sefa YAZAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 404

Session 2.12		11 NOVEMBER 2022 14:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-101	COMPARATIVE STUDY OF DEEP LEARNING FOR MASK DETECTION	Mohamad Taj Eddin ASHOUR, Dala KRAYEM, Asmaallah FALLAHA, Saed ALQARALEH	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 425
T-102	The Effect of Dielectric Substrate Thickness and the Length of Periodic Resonator Shape of Textile Fabric-Based Metamaterials on Absorption at X Band	Ediz ERDEM and Ahmet Hayrettin YÜZER	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 436
T-103	Halatlı ve Kayışlı Sistemlerde Kullanılan Asansör Motorlarının Performans Değerlendirmesi	Ahmet Fenercioğlu, Mücahit Soyaslan, Yusuf Avşar, Feyyaz Sarhan, Dağhan Atakay	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 443
T-104	Compressive and thermal behavior of double-network methacrylated κ -carrageenan/gellan gum based hydrogels	Yusuf Kanca and Bengi Özkahraman	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 516
T-105	COVID-19 Pandemi Sürecinin Başında ve Günümüzde Değişen Diş Hekimliği Hizmet, Korunma ve Önleme Uygulamalarına Yaklaşım	Yağmur Murat, Ayşe Dina Erdilek and Ümit Begüm Efes	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 450
T-106	Syntheses and characterizations of spiro cyclotriphosphazene derivatives bearing carbazole units	Hüseyin Akbaş	Turkey	Submission 452
T-107	Potential distribution of <i>Picea orientalis</i> L. in Turkey the scope of sustainable forestry	Ahmet ACARER, Oğuzhan ERFİDAN, M. Güvenç NEGİZ, Ahmet MERT	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 454
T-108	Production and characterization of polystyrene and cardboard sandwich panels covered with fiberboard	Orhan Kelleci, Süheyla Esin Köksal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 457
T-109	Elektrikli Otomobil Seçiminde Çok Kriterli Karar Verme: Borda Tümlleşik MULTIMOORA Yöntemi	Adnan Abdulvahitoğlu, Aslı Abdulvahitoğlu, Danişment VURAL	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 461
T-110	Development Study of Kalaodi Agrotourism Area in The City of Tidore Islands	Dini Sulfana Djufri, Muhammad Irfan	Indonesia, Turkey	Submission 463

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-111	Sathi Kaplamalı Üstyapı Tasarımında Mekanistik Yaklaşım	Yavuz ABUT	Turkey	Submission 467
T-112	The Influence of Turbulence Models on the Numerical Modelling of a 3D Wing in Ground Effect	Yavuz Hakan Özdemir, Taner Coşgun	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 469
T-113	Batı Avrupa Ülkelerinin Gelişmişlik Düzeylerinin Legatum Refah Endeksi Göstergeleri Bağlamında Analizi	Yusuf Şahin, Erdal Aydemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 471
T-114	FUCOM ve COPRAS Yöntemleriyle ERP Yazılımı Seçimi	Yusuf Şahin, Kenan Karagül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 474
T-115	Meslek Yüksekokulu Öğrencileri İçin Yaz Stajı Yazılımı	Sena TAŞ, Ercan AYKUT	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 475
T-116	First Case of Trhypochthoniellus longisetus (Acari: Trhypochthoniidae) in Malawi Blue Dolphin (Cyrtocara moorii)	Akif ER	Turkey	Submission 487
T-117	ANTIMICROBIAL, ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY AND DNA INTERACTIONS WITH 4-HYDROXYCOUMARIN PARTLY SUBSTITUTED 2-THIOPHENYLMETHYLSPIRO (N/N) CYCLOTRIPHOSPHAZENE COMPOUND	Berivan Töre, Leyla Açık, Güller Ballı, Aytuğ Okumuş, Gamze Elmas, Zeynel Kılıç	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 490
T-118	Antioxidant Activity Properties of Extract of Basil (Ocimum basilicum L.) Plant	Mohamed Rbaa, Burak TÜZÜN	Morocco, Turkey	Submission 493
T-119	Bor İçeren Topraklardan Nocardia Bakterilerinin İzolasyonu ve 16S rRNA Dizi Analizi	Kerem ÖZDEMİR, Metin ERTAŞ and Hamdullah SEÇKİN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 494
T-120	Heavy metal concentrations in estuarine waters of Giresun (Türkiye) coasts	Hazel BAYTAŞOĞLU	Turkey	Submission 515

Session 2.14		11 NOVEMBER 2022 15:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-121	Zerene Kaplıcası'ndan (Hakkari) İzole Edilen Bakterilerin Ekstraselüler Hidrolik Enzim Kapasitelerinin Belirlenmesi ve Karakterizasyonu	Nazım SEVEN, Metin ERTAŞ and Kerem ÖZDEMİR	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 498
T-122	Nakagami-m Sönümlenme ve Ters Gamma Gölgeleme Etkisi Altında Akıllı Yansıtıcı Yüzey Destekli Telsiz Haberleşme Sistemi Performans Analizi	Emir Aslandoğan	Turkey	Submission 512
T-123	Heat Transfer Characteristics of Al ₂ O ₃ -Water Based Nanofluid in a Double Pipe Heat Exchanger: Experimental and Numerical Study	Aycan ALTUN, Osman Nuri ŞARA	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 517
T-124	Gökkuşuğu alabalığı (Oncorhynchus mykiss) lensine yakından bir bakış	Süleyman Yüksel, Beste Demirci	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 519
T-125	Deri Tulum Peynirlerinden İzole Edilen Enterococcus ssp ait suşların Antioksidatif Aktivitelerinin Belirlenmesi	İpek SÖZER, Nihat AKIN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 528
T-126	OPTIMAL SIZING AND ALLOCATION OF DGS IN DISTRIBUTIONS SYSTEM BY USING HEURISTIC OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM	Rukiye B.AYMAZ, Mehmet Ali Yalçın and Talha Enes Gümüş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 535
T-127	MODULATION OF WALNUT SEED COAT EXTRACT ON OXIDATIVE STRESS IN HYPERLİPİDEMİC RENAL TİSSUE INDUCED BY TRİTON WR-1339	Esra Palabıyık, Ayse Nurseli Sulumer, Handan Uguz, Bahri Avcı, Seda Aşkın and Hakan Aşkın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 540
T-128	Bioactive Compounds and Total Antioxidant Activity of Cornus alba Leaf Extracts	Abayhan BURAN, Aykut TOPDEMİR and Rabia ÖZTÜRK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 567
T-129	Döngüsel Ekonomi Bakış Açısıyla Gıda Sektöründe Sürdürülebilir Tedarikçi Seçiminde Entropi Tabanlı Gri İlişkisel Analiz Yöntemi	Emel Yontar	Turkey	Submission 571
T-130	Kısacık (Ayvacık/Çanakkale-Türkiye) ve Civarındaki Kayaçların Ağır Metal/İz Element İçeriklerinin Çevre Jeokimyası Açısından İncelenmesi	Alaaddin Vural, Abdullah Kaygusuz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 586

Session 2.15		11 NOVEMBER 2022 15:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-131	PV/T SİSTEMLERDE NANOAKIŞKAN KULLANIMI	Hakan Dumrul, Edip Taşkesen	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 587
T-132	DA-DA Buck Dönüştürücü Tasarımında Adaptif PID Kontrolcünün Etkileri	Merve TÜRKTAM, M. Nuri ALMALI	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 593
T-133	Relations Between Odd Parts and Distinct Odd Parts of a Positive Integers	Büşra AL, Mustafa ALKAN	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 7
T-134	A Note on Fibonacci Numbers and Compositions	Büşra AL, Mustafa ALKAN	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 8
T-135	Compositions Restricted to the Number of Part	Büşra AL, Mustafa ALKAN	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 9
T-136	A Note on Relation Between Partitions Number and Odd Partitions Number For a Positive Integers	Büşra AL, Mustafa ALKAN	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 10
T-137	Karbon Ayak İzi Ve İklim Değişikliği	Sena TAŞ, Ercan AYKUT, Muhammet Cihat Mumcu, Kübra ERDOĞAN, Ali ÇETİNKAYA, Nevzat Yağız TOMBAL, İzzet YAVUZ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 11
T-138	Ayçiçeği'nin Dünyada ve Ülkemizde ki Mevcut Üretim Durumu ve Yüksek Oleik Asit İçeren Çeşitlerin Önemi	Nazire Gülşah Kütük Dinçel	Turkey	mail submission 12
T-139	Analytic hierarchy process-based multi-choice conic goal programming approach for the shift scheduling problem in the food industry	Derya Deliktaş	Turkey	Submission 620
T-140	GÜNCEL BARAJ HASARLARIN ANALİZİ YOLUYLA TASARIM ve İNŞAAT ALTERNATİFLERİNİN DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ	Alin ABA and Kasım YENİGÜN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 622

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-141	SOLAR ENERGY ANALYSIS BY USING DIFFERENT PACKAGE PROGRAMS	Huda Merzah AL-JIRYAWEE and Aslan İNAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 663
T-142	Influences of an Uncertain Impedance Boundary on the Natural Frequencies of a Composite Beam	Serkan GÜLER	Turkey	Submission 671
T-143	Investigation of interferon-gamma plasma levels in naïve and glatiramer acetate-treated multiple sclerosis patients	Mekselina Kalmaz, Birsen Can Demirdöğen and Semra Mungan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 703
T-144	Electrical Characterization of Carbon Nanotube Field-Effect Transistor	Halit Altuntaş, Feyza Öke-Altuntaş and S. Ravi P.Silva	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 707
T-145	Raman Characterization of Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes	Halit Altuntaş, Feyza Öke-Altuntaş and S. Ravi P.Silva	Turkey, Turkey, UK	Submission 712
T-146	Properties and Applications of Carbon Nanotubes	Feyza Öke-Altuntaş, Selin Sarıtan and Halit Altuntaş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 719
T-147	Gradyanların Histogramı Algoritması ve Evrişimli Sinir Ağları Kullanılarak Göğüs Xray Görüntü Sınıflandırması	Yunus Emre DEMİR, Abidin Çalıřkan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 241
T-148	At keřanesinin ultrasonik ekstraksiyonu: Taguchi optimizasyon	Mehmet Güldane, Hamza Bozkır	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 13
T-149	EGE BÖLGESİNDEN TOPLANAN ÇİĞ İNEK SÜT ÖRNEKLERİNDEN SIVI KROMATOĞRAFİ YÖNTEMİ (HPLC) İLE ANTİBİYOTİK KALINTILARININ BELİRLENMESİ	Büşra Aydın, İbrahim Bulduk and Safiye Elif Korcan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 14
T-150	DETERMINATION OF ANTIBIOTIC RESIDUES FROM RAW COW MILK SAMPLES COLLECTED FROM THE AEGEAN REGION BY LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY (HPLC)	Büşra Aydın, İbrahim Bulduk and Safiye Elif Korcan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 15

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-151	Investigation of Ceramic Welding Applicability to the Refractory Bricks at Room Temperature	Göktağ SUNGU and Alper İNCESU	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 508
T-152	Blok Zincir ve Kripto Paralar: Hukuki Açından İnceleme	Ümmühan AVCI, Serkan ATAMAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 545
T-153	Sürücüsüz Araçlar ve Kullanımı: Oluşabilecek Tehlikeler ve Hukuki Boyutu	Barış Tufantepe, Damla Bakım Tufantepe, Doç. Dr. Ümmühan Avcı	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 473
T-154	Elektronik Ticaret, Etik Kurallar ve Hukuki Boyut	Veysel ÇULHA, Ümmühan AVCI	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 551
T-155	Comparison of the change in nucleic acid molecule and the cell number at harvest time of Chlorella vulgaris microalgae	Osman Kök, İlhami Tüzün and Yaşar Aluç	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 713
T-156	PDMS Kompozit Tabanlı Piezodirençli Sensör Üretimi ve Karakterizasyonu	Esra ŞEN, Murat KALELİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 429
T-157	Doğrusal Olmayan Hat Akımı Altında Amorf ve Nanokristal Toroid Çekirdekli Elektromanyetik Hasatlayıcı Üzerine Bir İnceleme	Serdal Arslan	Turkey	Submission 483
T-158	Yer Etkisindeki Bir Kanatın Aerodinamik Yapısının HAD ile incelenmesi	Taner Cosgun, Yavuz Hakan Özdemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 468
T-159	Structural Investigations of (4-methoxyphenyl) methanaminium Chloride	Sevgi Kansız and Necmi Dege	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 472
T-160	Mechanical and High Temperature Resistance of Mortars with Crumb Elastic Polyurethane and Rubber Wood Added as Aggregate	Müzeyyen Balçıkanlı Bankir	Turkey	Submission 485

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-56	Elektrikli Araçlarda Kullanılan Lityum İyon Bataryaların Soğutulmasında Faz Değiştiren Malzemelerin Uygulanabilirliğinin İncelenmesi	Mehmet Zerrakki IŞIK and Ferhat AKKUŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 161
O-57	Kobalt katkılı Pt/C katalizörünün PEM yakıt pilin de anot ve katot katalizörü olarak kullanımı	Arzu EKİNCİ	Turkey	Submission 446
O-58	Investigation of Adhesion Strength of Al7075+ZK60 And Al7075+ZK61 Bimetal Composites	Emre ÖZTÜRK, Esmâ KESKİN, Hayrettin AHLATCI and Hüseyin ZENGİN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 560
O-59	Corrosion Behaviour of Dip Coated Polymer Films On 316L Stainless Steel	Rahma SHAABAN, Hayrettin AHLATCI, Antar ALALI ALKHALIL and Ammar Zeidan Ghailan ALSHEMARY	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 565

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-161	A Superparamagnetic Material Biosynthesis and using for Co ²⁺ Removal	Burcu Aydođdu, Muharrem İnce, Olcay Kaplan İnce, Hevidar Alp Kavlo	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 520
T-162	A Study on the General Perspective of Nanobeam	Burak Emre Yapanmıř	Turkey	Submission 518
T-163	Researching The Potential of Marble Waste in Turkey And The Use Places of This Waste	Gökhan Külekçi	Turkey	Submission 530
T-164	Antibiyotik Yüklü Jelatin Mikropartiküllerin Üretimi	Derya Erduđan and Aslıhan Kazan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 543
T-165	Determination of hardness with Schmidt hammer in clay quarries The Case of Bayburt-Gümüşhane Turkey	Gökhan Külekçi	Turkey	Submission 547
T-166	A Computational Study on the Corrosion Inhibition Performances of Some Organic Structures	Mustafa Elik	Turkey	Submission 556
T-167	Diř Renklenmeleri ve Güncel Tedavileri	Sevdiye Burke, Begüm Güray EFES	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 595
T-168	POLLEN MORPHOLOGY INVESTIGATIONS OF ECONOMICALLY IMPORTANT <i>Pyraecantha coccinea</i> M.Roem. (Rosaceae) TAXON GROWING IN ESKİŐEHİR	Okan SEZER, İsmühan POTOĐLU ERKARA	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 484
T-169	Effect of different pH conditions on anionic dye biosorption from wastewater using chestnut bark	Nurřah KÜTÜK	Turkey	mail submission 16
T-170	Elimination of vibrations using magnetic field in the quarter-car and bridge interaction model	Mustafa Erođlu, Mehmet Akif Koç, İsmail Esen, Recep Kozan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 608

Session 2.20		11 NOVEMBER 2022 17:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-171	Mikrobiyal Levan Biyopolimerinin Potansiyel Uygulamaları	Furkan Öztürk, Nurcihan Hacıoğlu Doğru	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 609
T-172	Resorsinol-Formaldehit ve Polieterimid Polimer Karışımının Termal, Morfolojik ve Yapısal Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi	Sefa ARAS and Derya ÜNLÜ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 612
T-173	Biyoetanölün Üretimi ve Saflaştırılmasında Hidrofobik/Hidrofilik Hibrit Membran Prosesi	Buse Ünal, Muhammed Taha Nalbant and Derya Ünlü	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 613
T-174	Preparation of Thermoset Nanocomposites Containing HNT-Amine by Cationic Photopolymerization	Seda BEKİN AÇAR and M. Atilla TAŞDELEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 625
T-175	Engelli Taşıma Lifti Tasarımı ve Analizi	Mustafa BÜYÜKKAYIN, Ömer SEÇGİN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 641
T-176	EPS Geoföam Malzemelerin Geoteknik Mühendisliğinde Uygulamaları	Ekin Kendal Duman, Müge Balkaya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 646
T-177	Transfer Öğrenme Yöntemleri ile Meyve Yapraklarında Hastalık Tespiti	Hazel Bozcu, Burakhan Çubukçu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 650
T-178	Nokta Direnç Kaynağı ile Birleştirilen Farklı Dayanım Seviyelerine Sahip DP600-DP1200 Çeliklerin Mekanik Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi	Emre Katılmış and Muhammed Elitaş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 652
T-179	Implementation of MPPT algorithm for solar photovoltaic cell by comparing ANN and P&O method	Alaa Kareem AL. JANABI and Aslan İNAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 654
T-180	Computational Fluid Dynamics Analysis of an Opposed-Piston Two-Stroke Compression Ignition Engine	Ramazan Şener	Turkey	Submission 656

Session 2.21		11 NOVEMBER 2022 18:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-181	A Note on Applications of Error Correcting Output Codes on Detecting Hate Speech in Twitter Data	Vildan Mercan, Sümeyra Bedir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 657
T-182	DEMİRYOLLARINDAKİ LOKOMOTİF İHTİYACININ YAPAY ZEKÂ VE REGRESYON YÖNTEMLERİ İLE MODELLENMESİ	Ömer Faruk CANSIZ, Ali UZUN, Olcay GENÇ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 669
T-183	Analytical Hierarchy Process Approach in Metal Matrix Composites	Yaşam KANDEMİR, Temel VAROL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 673
T-184	Endüstriyel Atık Malzemeler Kullanılarak Üretilen Geopolimer Harçların Durabilite Özelliklerinin Araştırılması	Özlem Çavdar, Hülya Temizer	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 677
T-185	The Effects of Pretreatments on Antioxidant Properties of Microwave Dried Apple Slices	Alev Akpınar Borazan	Turkey	Submission 681
T-186	Classification of Transcription Factor DNA in the Brassica Plant Species by Deep Learning	Ali Burak Öncül	Turkey	Submission 689
T-187	Aktif ve Pasif Dengeleme Yapabilen Çoklu Kurşun Asit Batarya Yönetim Sistemi	Muhammet YİĞİTER, Hüseyin Oktay ALTUN, Sinan KIVRAK, Emre TURAN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 690
T-188	MACBETH ve Gri İlişkisel Analiz Kullanılarak Piyasaya Sürülecek Bilgisayar Oyun Karakterlerine Karar Verilmesi	Mehmet Onur OLGUN	Turkey	Submission 691
T-189	Dişli Ve Kaplin Üretimi Yapan Bir Firmanın Metot Etüdü İle Süreç İyileştirilmesi	Mehmet Onur OLGUN	Turkey	Submission 693
T-190	Electrical and flexural properties of silver-doped graphene reinforced carbon fiber epoxy composites	Hülya Kaftelen Odabaşı, Mustafa Özdemir, Akın Odabaşı and Murat Baydoğan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 699

Session 2.22		11 NOVEMBER 2022 18:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-191	Green synthesis of Magnetic Nanomaterial for Wastewater Treatment: An Experimental Design Approach	Hevidar Alp Kavlo, Olcay Kaplan İnce, Muharrem İnce and Burcu Aydođdu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 710
T-192	Comparison of Machine Learning Models Performances in Predicting Diabetes Probability	Muhammed Yıldırım, Eser Sert	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 716
T-193	Beyin Tümörü Teşhisinde CNN-FL Modeli Ağ Performansı Karşılaştırılması	Elif Ebru Çakı, Tamer Aslan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 717
T-194	Properties and Applications of Carbon Nanotubes	Feyza Öke Altuntaş, Selin Sarıtan and Halit Altuntaş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 719
T-195	Derin Zemin Karıştırma Kolonlarının Yapım ve Prosedürünün İncelenmesi	Esmâ Alan and Müge Balkaya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 721
T-196	Dizel bir motorda geliştirilen yeni yanma odası geometrisinin performans ve emisyonlara etkisi	İlker Temizer, Ömer Cihani	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 722
T-197	An overview: Haloculture and Biosaline Agriculture For A Sustainable Economy	Fadime Eryılmaz Pehlivan	Turkey	Submission 727
T-198	Effect of Nanoparticle Reinforcement on Thermal Properties of Composite Materials	Yusuf KEPİR, Fatih UNAL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 730
T-199	Yük Taşımacılığındaki Elektrikli Araçların Seçim Kriterlerinin Bulanık AHP Yöntemi ile Değerlendirilmesi	Onur Derse	Turkey	Submission 731
T-200	Mechanical properties of slag-based geopolymers	Özer Sevim, Khaled Mahdi AL-Qudaih	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 734

Session 2.23		11 NOVEMBER 2022 19:00-20:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-201	Investigation of Simulation Based Stochastic and Random Characteristics of the FitzHugh-Nagumo Model	Zafer Bekiryazıcı	Turkey	Submission 735
T-202	Evaluation of Manisa Celal Bayar University's Thirty Years of Scientific Contribution through Web of Science Resources	Muhammet Damar, Güzin Özdağoğlu and Ömer Aydın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 743
T-203	Research on Biodiversity of Vespidae (Insecta Hymenoptera) Wasps of Cappadocia	Aysel Kekillioğlu	Turkey	Submission 748
T-204	An Evaluation of Invasive Insects and Their Effects	Aysel Kekillioğlu, Ömer Eren Bostan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 749
T-205	Investigation of Pollination Biology and Morphology of <i>B. terrestris</i> L. 1758 (Insecta:Hymenoptera) Species in Boraginaceae Family	Aysel Kekillioğlu, Ebru Kunduraç	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 750
T-206	Gökkuşuğu alabalıklarında ülser oluşumu ile ilişkili <i>Bacillus cereus</i> enfeksiyonu	Ezgi Dinçtürk	Turkey	Submission 754
T-207	Apitherapy and Its Place in Our Daily Lives	Hacer Karabulut and Yağmur Ünver	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 757
T-208	Cyclic Voltammetry studies of PABA as Electroactive Material for Flow Batteries	Taha Yasin EKEN, Ömer Yunus GÜMÜŞ, Deniz UZUNSOY	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 765
T-209	Tabakalı Kompozit Kirişlerde Fiber Yönlenme Açılarının Yapının Doğal Frekansına Olan Etkisinin İncelenmesi	Sinan MARAŞ and Abdullah Tahir ŞENSOY	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 769
T-210	Optimal placement of Multi distribution generators Based on particle swarm optimization in a Radial Distribution network in Amman-Jordan	Mohammad Al Zaben, Mustafa Turan and Talha Enes Gümüş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 771

Session 2.24		11 NOVEMBER 2022 19:00-20:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-211	Investigation of the Impact of the Pandemic on the Power System Operations	Ali Ajder	Turkey	Submission 777
T-212	Dalga Enerjisi Teknolojileri	Mustafa YILDIZ, Hasan GÜLER, Zeynep Bala DURANAY	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 510
T-213	Structural Analysis of the Nose Landing Gear of a Fighter Aircraft	Gözde AYDIN, İbrahim ÖZKOL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 500
T-214	The enzymes role in the 2-Hydroxyglutarate production	Esra BULUT ATALAY	Turkey	Submission 524
T-215	Effect of Carbon Nanotube Doping on Electrical Properties in ZA27/MWCNT Composites	Rüstem Yılmazel, Mustafa Yasin Erten, Muharrem Pul	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 536
T-216	Seramik Sektöründe Yalın Üretim Teknikleri	Onur ORDU and Rahmiye Zerrin YARBAY	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 548
T-217	Sosyal Mühendislik Yöntemlerinden Ortalama Saldırıların Oluşumu ve Olası Etkileri	Semih Çakır, Onur GÜRSEL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 596
T-218	Cornus Alba Reinforced Polyester-Epoxy Hybrid Composite Production and Characterization	Abayhan Buran, Murat Ersin Durğun and Ercan Aydoğmuş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 18
T-219	PASSIVE STRUCTURAL CONTROL	Şebnem Metin, Duygu Öztürk	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 601
T-220	Endüstriyel Nesnelerin İnternetinde (IIoT) PLC Makinelerinin SCADA Sisteminde Oluşturduğu Zafiyetler ve Siber Saldırıları	Semih Çakır, Sevet Emre Bozacıoğlu, Nuri Bozacıoğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 605

Session 2.25		11 NOVEMBER 2022 20:00-21:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-221	Benzin ve Motorin Tüketimini Etkileyen Faktörlerin Değerlendirilmesi	Mehmet Güneş, Mehmet Soydan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 668
T-222	Trend Analizi Yöntemleriyle Kuraklık Etkisinin Değerlendirilmesi: Batı Karadeniz Havzası Devrekâni Örnekleme	Hakan AYDIN, Kasım YENİGÜN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 686
T-223	Antikanser Etkili Venomlar	Rana Elif Akkuş	Turkey	Submission 700
T-224	Otsu ve Rocchio Metotlarıyla Beyin Tümörü Tespiti	Rıfat Aşlıyan	Turkey	Submission 723
T-225	Dünyadaki Bazı Ülkelerde Değer Yönetimi ve Değer Mühendisliği Bilinirlik ve Uygulama Düzeyi ve Türkiye'deki Durum	Nusret MUM, Şenay ATABAY and Durmuş AKKAYA	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 728
T-226	Investigating Microstructure of Resistance Spot Welded Dissimilar TWIP1000/22MnB5 Boron Steel	Fatih ÖZEN	Turkey	Submission 736
T-227	In Silico Genotoxic and Carcinogenic Potential Assessment of Bilastine	Nihan AKINCI KENANOĞLU, Şefika Nur DEMİR and Ahmet Ali BERBER	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 746
T-228	Elektrikli Araç Şarj Yöntemleri ve İki Yönlü Şarj Cihazlarının İncelenmesi	Behçet Kocaman	Turkey	Submission 783
T-229	Gerçek Zamanlı Gömülü Sistemlerde Enerji Tüketiminin Azaltılması İçin Dinamik Voltaj ve Frekans Ölçeklendirme (DVFS) Algoritmaları	Sibel Kaplan, Ayşegül Yaman, Sonay Duman, Abdullah Elewi	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 786
T-230	Nesnelerin İnterneti (IoT) Tabanlı Yüz Tanıma Uygulaması	Ezgi UYGUR, Vedat MARTTİN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 789

Session 2.26		11 NOVEMBER 2022 20:00-21:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-231	İstatistik-Klinik Önemlilik (Anlamlılık) ve Klinik Önemli Asgari Değişim	Sıddık Keskin	Turkey	Submission 819
T-232	TÜRKİYE'DE BİYOTEKNOLOJİ GİRİŞİMCİLİĞİ ÖNÜNDEKİ ENGELLERİN CRITIC VE SWARA YÖNTEMLERİ İLE AĞIRLIKLANDIRILMASI	Nazlı SEYHAN	Turkey	Submission 822
T-233	Genotoxicity evaluation of thaumatin, a natural sweetener: An in silico assessment	Nihan AKINCI KENANOĞLU, Şefika Nur DEMİR and Ahmet Ali BERBER	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 827
T-234	Manyetik Alanın Bir Isı Borusunun Termal Performansına Etkisi	Duygu Yılmaz Aydın, Emrullah Aydın ve Metin Gürü	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 841
T-235	İçi boş silindirik parçalarda darbeli (pulse) elektrokimyasal işlemin kanal geometrisine etkisi	Semih Ekrem Anıl, Hasan Demirtaş ve Adnan Kalaycı	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 847
T-236	The Effects of Doxorubicin on the mRNA Expression of Some Heat Shock Protein 70 (Hsp70) Family Members in Rat Liver and the Modulatory Role of Tannic Acid	Neslihan Ozturk, Hamid Ceylan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 850
T-237	Optimum insulation thickness and energy saving potential on walls	Yusuf KEPİR, Fatih UNAL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 858
T-238	Dıştan Dişli Pompalarda Farklı Dönme Hızlarının Pompa Performansına Etkisinin HAD Analizi ile İncelenmesi	Üsâme Ali Usca and Mahir Uzun	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 863
T-239	İkili Ankraj Gruplarının Çekme Dayanımının Belirlenmesi	Özer Özdemir and Özlem Çalışkan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 866
T-240	Granit Plakalarının Evrişimli Sinir Ağları ile Sınıflandırılması	Fatih Ziyalı, Nesibe Yalçın ve Sibel Ünalı	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 694

Session 2.27		11 NOVEMBER 2022 15:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-60	Ectoparasitic Diseases Prevention and Control Methods	Burak ŞAHİN, Pelin ŞAHİN, Uğur USLU	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 724
O-61	Cam elyaf yüzey kaplamaları için su bazlı poliüretan dispersiyonlarının sentezi ve karakterizasyonu	Ayşe Begüm CURA, Mithat ÇELEBİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 720
O-62	From lentil waste to porous carbon material by microwave-induced chemical activation: Application in removal of toxic organic dyes	Hasan Saygılı and Gülbahar Akkaya Saygılı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 698
O-63	Triboelectric Nanogenerators used in Wind Energy Harvesting	Abdulkerim Okbaz	Turkey	Submission 685

Session 2.28		11 NOVEMBER 2022 21:00-22:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-241	Security and Privacy Challenges in Fog Computing	Merve YILDIRIM	Turkey	Submission 702
T-242	Ultra Wideband (UWB) L Grounded Extended Radiator Disc Antenna Design and Analysis for Positioning Systems in Smart Factories	Hüseyin Özdil, Adnan Kaya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 753
T-243	Son Adım Ev Dışı Teslimat Yöntemi Seçim Kriterlerinin Çok Kriterli Karar Verme ile İncelenmesi	Şaban Fatih YILMAZ, Neslihan DEMİREL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 773
T-244	Forming a Social, Environmental and Economical Symbiotic Structure of Organized Industrial Zones within the Perspective of Sustainable Education, a Case Study: OSTİM Technical University, Ankara	Zeliha Şahin Çağlı, İbrahim Baran Uslu, Hikmet Bal, Songül Çalış Arat, Pelin Tören Özgün, Birsen Yüceses, Zehra Sever, Merve Yıldız, Barış Gürçan Hakanoğlu, Aydan Burcu Başer, Ali Güner, Gazi Uğraş, Mehmet Duahan Adıgüzel	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 781
T-245	Comparison of the Effect of MFCC and GTCC Features on Determining the Ideal Recording Time for Body Sound Location Identification	Osman Ballı, Yakup Kutlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 788
T-246	BÜYÜK ÖLÇEKLİ İLERİ BİYOLOJİK ATIKSU ARITMA TESİSİNE AİT HAVALANDIRMA HAVUZU KAPASİTESİNİN KİNETİK DEĞERLENDİRME İLE ARTIRILMASI	Cemal Samet ERGİN, Sakine UĞURLU KARAAĞAÇ ans Hayrettin Güçlü İNSEL	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 795
T-247	Ultra Yüksek Performanslı Nano-Selüloz Fiberlerle Üretilmiş Eğilebilir Betonların Mekanik Özellikleri ve Yapısal Davranışlarının Araştırılması	Begüm Peker, Ezgi Gürbüz ve Savaş Erdem	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 815
T-248	Total phenol and flavonoid contents, and antioxidant capacity of Silybum marianum L. Gaertner grown in Turkey	Erten Akbel, İbrahim Bulduk	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 828
T-249	Effect of Particle and Porosity Content on Tensile Strength and Wear Response of SiC/A356 Composites	Coşkun Yolcu and Fatih Kahraman	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 832
T-250	Investigation of the Grain Refinement Potency of Niobium and KBF4 Salt for AlSi5 and AlSi12 Alloys by in-situ Inoculation	Coşkun Yolcu and Fatih Kahraman	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 833

Session 2.29		11 NOVEMBER 2022 21:00-22:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-251	The transition from Industry 4.0 to a human-centric Industry 5.0: a bibliometric analysis	OURANIA ARETA HIZIROĞLU, YOUSEF BARJAKLY	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 837
T-252	Anodizasyon Yöntemiyle Titanyum Dioksit Nanotüp Üretimi ve Hidrojen Gazı Algılaması	Lütfi Bilal TAŞYÜREK, Esmem IŞIK, İbrahim IŞIK, Necmettin KILINÇ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 857
T-253	Evaluation of Important Land Characteristics of Malya Agricultural Enterprise Soils in GIS Environment	Yavuz Şahin Turgut, Yakup Kenan Koca	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 864
T-254	Maximum transition temperatures for Al-added bulk Bi-2212 superconductor crystallized in the optimum crystal structure	Muhammed ÖZ and Gürçan YILDIRIM	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 869
T-255	Bal ve Balın Bileşiminde Bulunan Doğal Enzimler, Organik Asitler ve Mineraller	Muhammed ERCAN, Mehmet AKBULUT, Hacer ÇOKLAR, Bayram YURT	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 874
T-256	Kafatası İmplantı/Protezi Üretimi İçin Alternatif Bir Yöntem	Ömer Seçgin	Turkey	Submission 876
T-257	Importance of Edge Computing in Critical Manufacturing Systems: FPGA Implementation	Tuncay Ercan	Turkey	Submission 744
T-258	BOR İÇEREN DİŞ PORSELENİ ÜRETİMİ	Ahmed Ismael M. Shareef ALABOOSH, Mevlüt GÜRBÜZ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 737
T-259	OKUL SAĞLIĞI HEMŞİRELİĞİ BAKIŞ AÇISIYLA: ADÖLESAN DÖNEMDEKİ BİREYLERİN PROBLEM ÇÖZME BECERİSİ ve İRRASYONEL İNANÇLARI ARASINDAKİ İLİŞKİNİN BELİRLENMESİ	Feyza KARAGÖZ, Esmem KABASAKAL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 438
T-260	Effect of sulfuric acid and seawater exposure on physical and mechanical behavior of different concretes	Ahmet Emin Kurtoğlu	Turkey	Submission 479

Session 2.30		11 NOVEMBER 2022 22:00-23:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-261	Balda Bulunan Başlıca Aminoasitler	Bayram YURT, Muhammed ERCAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 873
T-262	NLP-based SVM classification algorithm for causation of marine inspections	Samet Bicen	Turkey	Submission 768
T-263	KATI ÇÖZELTİYLE GÜÇLENDİRİLMİŞ FERRİTİK KÜRESEL DÖKME DEMİRLERİN AŞINMA DİRENCİNİN İNCELENMESİ	Harun ÇUĞ and Batuhan ÖZUSTA	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 787
T-264	Investigation of Microstructural and Mechanical Properties of Hardox 400, AISI304L And St52 Quality Steels Combined By Mig Welding Method	Harun ÇUĞ and Arif SAVAŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 762
T-265	ALÜMİNYUM MATRİSLİ SİLİSYUM KARBÜR VE VANADYUM KARBÜR İLAVELİ HİBRİT KOMPOZİT ÜRETİMİ VE KARAKTERİZASYONU	Harun ÇUĞ and Batuhan ÖZUSTA	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 888
T-266	BUSER TRANSKÜTANÖZ ELEKTRİKSEL SİNİR STİMÜLATÖRÜ CİHAZI TASARIMI	Büşra LEVENT, Büşranur BARIŞ, Buse Selin SAZAKLIOĞLU, Gökhan NUR, Elvan AK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 661
T-267	Evaluation of Auction Features Using Fuzzy QFD in a Business Process Reengineering Approach	Ayça Maden	Turkey	Submission 887
T-268	Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemi Tabanlı Trafik Sirkülasyon Planı Oluşturulması	Yavuz DELİCE	Turkey	Submission 886
T-269	Genel Özellikleri ile PCAmix	Sıddık Keskin	Turkey	mail submission 26
T-270	ISM 2.4 GHz Band Antenna Model for RF Energy Harvesting Systems	Cem Gocen, Ismail Akdag, Mehmet Ali Belen, Peyman Mahouti, Adnan Kaya, Merih Palandoken	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 480

Session 2.31		11 NOVEMBER 2022 22:00-23:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-271	Creating a Database for a Ground Motion Prediction Equation of Aegean Region	Şule Sena GÜNGÖR, Evren SEYREK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 892
T-272	INVESTIGATION ON MICROSTRUCTURAL, HARDNESS AND CORROSION PROPERTIES OF ZW21 CASTING ALLOYS	Kenza DJEBARI, Yunus TÜREN, Hayrettin AHLATCI	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 676
T-273	Düşük Maliyetli Soğutulabilir İnsülin Kalem Kutusunun Tasarım ve Prototip İmalatı	Mustafa Güneş, Abdulhamit Sevgi and Çiğdem Serdengeçti	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 715
T-274	Çok Delikli Akış Şartlandırıcı Plakalarda Basınç Kaybını Azaltmak için Optimum Delik Pah Açısının Deneysel Yöntemle Araştırılması	Hasan DÜZ and Ramazan ÇİFTÇİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 816
T-275	(s,S) Envanter Sisteminin Etki-Dayanıklılık Güvenilirliği	Özge BALTA, Sevcan DEMİR ATALAY	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 842
T-276	In silico studies and structure activity relationships of picolinic acid derivatives as α -glucosidase inhibitors	Fatih Sönmez and Davut Avcı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 829
T-277	Molecular docking studies of Zn(II) and Mn(II) complexes of 6-bromopicolinate as α -glucosidase agents	Fatih Sönmez and Davut Avcı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 831
T-278	Genome-Wide Analysis and Characterization of the PYL Gene Family under Drought and Salt Stress in Phaseolus vulgaris	Zeynep Aksevim, Burak Muhammed Öner, Selman Muslu, Ayşe Gül Kasapoğlu, Murat İsiyel, Ahmed Sidar Aygören, Esra Yaprak, Sümeyra Uçar, Emre İlhan, Murat Aydın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 778
T-279				
T-280				

Session 3.1		12 NOVEMBER 2022 09:00-10:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-1	The impact of diabetes on male fertility: a meta-analysis	Yamina BELKHIRI, Souheyla BENBIA and Fella HÏBACHE	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3
Y-2	Examine the influence of EDM input parameters on the surface roughness of cryogenically treated Nimonic 80A	Jasanpreet Singh	India	Submission 9
Y-3	Elaboration of carbon steel samples coated with Alumina (AL2O3) For Anticorrosion application	karima Amara Korba	Algeria	Submission 11
Y-4	Study of n-butane Isomerization on WO3/ZrO2	Zahira MOHAMED SEGHIR, Amina MEZOUAGH	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 12
Y-5	Calculates the internal parameters of a pv panel with and without PCM cooling	MAIFI Lyes, AGROUI Kamel, HIOUAL Ouided, CHARI Abdelhamid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 15
Y-6	Assessment of two seasons on the performance of a local biological wastewater treatment plant	Fouzia Benoudjit and Hachemi Messaoud	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 21
Y-7	The effect of heat stress on male fertility: a meta-analysis	Yamina BELKHIRI, Souheyla BENBIA, Nour EL Houda BOUALI, Abir IKHLEF	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 23
Y-8	Conditions On The Normality and Hypo-normality of the Operators in Hilbert Space	Benali Abdelkader	Algeria	Submission 25
Y-9	Particle and Current Density of Ultra Cold Fermionics In Rapid Rotating Gas	Amina BERKANE, Soheyb MEDJEDEL	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 26
Y-10	Study the parameters of the durability and the cathodic protection of the pipeline coating	Benalia Kouini, Khaoula Boukerroucha and Louiza Halimi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 32

Session 3.2		12 NOVEMBER 2022 09:00-10:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-11	Neural networks prediction of flexural properties of gypsum plaster reinforced with jute fibers	Messaouda Boumaaza, Ahmed Belaadi and Mostefa Bourchak	Algeria, Algeria, Saudi Arabia	Submission 40
Y-12	Application of the Extended Finite Element Method to Assessment of Rock Slopes	TALEB Hosni Abderrahmane, GUEMIDI Ismahene and RAHMANI. Abdallah Yacine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 45
Y-13	Optimization of the borehole jet pump design	Denys Panevnyk	Ukraine	Submission 46
Y-14	Characterization Of CeO2 Nano powders synthesized by auto-combustion.	Wissam BOUCHAL, Faïçal DJANI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 48
Y-15	Antioxidant and Antidiabetic Activities of Hexane Extract of Ricinus communis Linn. (Castor Bean or Oil Plant)	Nweje-Anyalowu Paul Chukwuemeka, Ihuomah Victor Emeka, Anyalogbu Ernest Anayochukwu Aniemeka and Nweje-Anyalowu Gift Nkiru	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 51
Y-16	Effects of some physico-chemical pretreatments on the germination of seeds of Melia azedarach	Ayoub Allam, Abdelkrim Kefifa, Mohamed Zouidi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 52
Y-17	Control of properties morphological and opto-electronic of nanostructured Silicon for Solar Cells	Leila Harkat, Ghania Fortas, Nabil Khelifati, Boudjemaa Bouaouina, Chahinaz Nasraoui, Amar Manseri, Faouzi Kezzoula	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 53
Y-18	Study of the kinetics of polyphenol extraction	S.HAYA, R.RIHANI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 54
Y-19	Paper Optimal control of various linear pdes with incomplete data	Achab Fatma, Abdelhak Hafdallah	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 60
Y-20	Identification of the source term in coupled system using an optimal control framework	Achab Fatma, Abdelhak Hafdallah and imad rezzoug	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 61

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-21	The Effect of Initial Mechanical Properties on the Stability of a Slope by C-Phi Reduction (Numerical Analysis)	TALEB Hosni Abderrahmane, GUEMIDI Ismahene	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 67
Y-22	Extraction and characterization of microcrystalline cellulose from fruit bunch branches fibres of date palm trees	Benalia Kouini, Amina Hachaichi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 70
Y-23	Phytochemistry, HPLC profile and antioxidant activity of extracts of fenugreek (<i>Trigonella foenum graecum</i> L.)	Ahmed HAZEL, Ouahiba MOUMEN and Wardia OULIDALI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 74
Y-24	Testing LAD2 of Harvesting Electric Roads	Mohammed Alaa Alwafaie, Bela Kovacs	Hungary, Hungary	Submission 76
Y-25	On the quasilinear hyperbolic equations with a nonlinear damping and source terms	Abir Bounaama, Maouni Messaoud	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 77
Y-26	Existence of solutions for a coupled system of hyperbolic wave equations	Abir Bounaama	Algeria	Submission 78
Y-27	A Delay Mathematical Model of Chronic Myeloid Leukemia Under Treatment.	Mohamed HELAL, Abdelkader LAKMECHE and Chaymaa BOUSAHLA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 79
Y-28	Adjusted risk premium for heavy-tailed losses under dependence	Helal Nacera, Ouadjed Hakim	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 80
Y-29	Estimation of the conditional tail expectation for a stable AR(1) process	Mahiddine Abderrahim	Algeria	Submission 81
Y-30	Modeling the extremal behavior of the heavy-tailed max-autoregressive process	Moulay Abdelkader	Algeria	Submission 82

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-31	Modeling the Federal Fund rate data with infinite variance process	Mami Tawfiq Fawzi	Algeria	Submission 83
Y-32	On Some Hybrid q-Difference Equations with Delay	Abdelkrim Salim	Algeria	Submission 84
Y-33	Parametric study of the stability of diaphragm walls	Azzeddine LAHMADI	Algeria	Submission 85
Y-34	Blow up of solution for laminated Timoshenko beams with nonlinear weights	Baibeche Sabah	Algeria	Submission 88
Y-35	A comparative experiment of cement materials' characteristics composite from expanded and raw cork granules waste	Merabti.Salem and Boudina Abdellah	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 89
Y-36	Development, characterisation and evaluation of the antibacterial activity of calcium fluorohydroxyapatite	AGSOUS Maissa, KHIREDINE Hafit, YALA Sabeha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 93
Y-37	A Coupled Caputo Hadamard Fractional Dierential System with Multipoint Boundary Conditions	Samir Aibout, Said Abbast, Mouffak Benchohrat and Martin Bohner	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, USA	Submission 94
Y-38	Design, Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization, DFT, docking studies and biological evaluation of novel 2-oxo-1,2- dihydroquinoline derivatives	Ayoub El-mrabet, Youssef Kandri Rodi, Skalli Mohamed Khalid, Amal Haoudi, Ahmed Mazzah	Morrocco, Morrocco, Morrocco, Morrocco, France	Submission 97
Y-39	A review on development of bio-active 2-oxo-1,2-dihydroquinoline derivatives:Recent advances	Ayoub El-mrabet, Youssef Kandri Rodi, Skalli Mohamed Khalid, Amal Haoudi, Ahmed Mazzah	Morrocco, Morrocco, Morrocco, Morrocco, France	Submission 99
Y-40	impact of annealing temperature on the physical properties of copper oxide thin films prepared by sol-gel technique	Boumezrag Maria Nor El yakin, Said Lakel and kenza Almi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 56

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-41	Existence and uniqueness for a Ginzburg-Landau system for superconductivity	Fares Yazid and Fatima Siham Djeradi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 86
Y-42	Exponential stability of solutions to nonlinear time-varying delay systems of neutral type equations with periodic coefficients	Fatima Siham Djeradi and Fares Yazid	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 87
Y-43	Basics of well jet pump renovation	Denys Panevnyk, Oleksandr Panevnyk	Ukraine, Ukraine	Submission 72
Y-44	The abrasive wear behavior of a thermochemically treated supermartensitic stainless steel	Khokha Lalaoui, A. E. Derradji, Samira Tlili, M. Z. Touhami	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 102
Y-45	PET images reconstruction using analytical and iterative methods	Benyelles Asma, Korti Amel	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 92
Y-46	Influence of heat treatment on the microstructure and mechanical properties of Al-Si cast alloy	Noura Traiaia, Abdennacer Lemoui and Samira Tlili	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 107
Y-47	Correlation between the propagation velocity of Rayleigh waves and the strength of hardened concrete	Rafika Aissani, Dellagi Amira, Taibi Billal, Kamal Abdelli and Tarek Boutkedjirt	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 36
Y-48	The extreme behavior of a regularly varying max-autoregressive process	Moulay Abdelkader	Algeria	Submission 114
Y-49	Influence of the stationary phase in HPLC Method Development for the Determination of Linezolid Drugs	Amina Missoum, Fatiha Malki and Abderrezak Hamdi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 121
Y-50	Long-term strain of RC beams: Experimental study and finite element analysis	Nefissa Belkacem, Farid Bouziadi, Abdelkader Haddi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 127

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-51	Synthesis and characterization of a modified hydroxyapatite for methylene blue removal	Aghilas Brahmi, Salima Ziani, Salima Aitali	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 130
Y-52	A Novel Particle Swarm Optimization-based Markovian Paradigm for Simulating the Deterioration of Slab on grade in Healthcare Facilities	Reem Ahmed, Eslam Mohammed Abdelkader, Ahmed Assad, Tarek Zayed and Fuzhan Nasiri	Canada, Hong Kong, Egypt, Canada	Submission 73
Y-53	Dynamic Background Subtraction in Moving Object Detection on Modified	Musa Genemo	Ethiopia	Submission 133
Y-54	Optimization of MPPT commands used for the control of photovoltaic systems	samira boumous, zouhir boumous, yacine djeghader	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 111
Y-55	Detection of short circuit faults in inverters by tolerant control	Z.Boumous, S.Boumous, Y.Djeghader, M.Benaoudj	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 118
Y-56	Neutral Partial Hyperbolic Fractional Differential Inclusions with Finite Delay in Fréchet Spaces	Mohamed Helal	Algeria	Submission 62
Y-57	Gasohydrodynamics of movement of gas-liquid mixture in formation-well system	Gunel Alizada	Azerbaijan	Submission 116
Y-58	Forming process of the nanostructured Cr70 Co30 powders mixture	Achraf Djallel eddine sid, Dekhil Leila, Amina grairia, Latifa kahloul	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 132
Y-59	Harmonic Filtering in Steel Plant Using Passive Filter	Yacine Djeghader, Reda Rouaibia, Zouhir Boumous and Samira Boumous	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 34
Y-60	Evaluation of Real-Time Background Subtraction Technique for Moving Object Detection Using Fast-Independent Component Analysis in Video Surveillance	Naoum Abderrahmane, Boumehed Meriem, Alshaqaqi Belal, Kandouci Chahinaz	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 63

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
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Y-62	Effect of the Annealing Temperature on the optical and Electrical Properties of Bromine- Doped Indium Oxide thin Films Deposited by Ultrasonic Spray	Bourhefir Ranida, Attaf Abdellah, Saidi Hanane and Hamani Nadjette	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 41
Y-63	AVERTING NETWORK SECURITY AND PRIVACY INTRUDER IN WBANs: A BRIEF SURVEY AND ITS CHALLENGES	Matthew Iyobhebhe, Eleje N. E , Chikani N.I, Onah M. C	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	mail submission 1
Y-64	A ROUTING PROTOCOL FOR STABILIZING ENERGY UTILIZATION IN WBANs: A BRIEF SURVEY AND CHALLENGES	Matthew Iyobhebhe, Eleje N. E , Chikani N.I, Onah M. C	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	mail submission 2
Y-65	Ab-initio Investigation of Electronic, Magnetic, Elastic and Thermoelectric Properties of Heusler Co ₂ ZrAl Alloy	Gherici Remil, Ali Zitouni, Samira Charid and Mohamed Matougui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 140
Y-66	The impact of Mg dilution of the structural, microstructural, and optical properties of ZnO films by the USP method	Roguai Sabrina, Djelloul Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 141
Y-67	Study of the structural, microstructural, and optical properties of ZnO thin films prepared by spray pyrolysis method	Roguai Sabrina, Djelloul Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 142
Y-68	Synthesis of 2-alkyl imidazolines and its derivatives 2-alkyl imidazolinium cationic surfactants from lamb fatty acid	Mohamed Nadjib REBIZI, Saber Oumerich, Ragadia Aissaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 100
Y-69	Socio-economic and cultural aspects of Municipal Solid Waste Management.	Housseem Hachemi, Seladji Chakib, Latifa Negadi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 146
Y-70	Contribution to the rationalization and control of the consumption electrical energy in industry (case study)	Mohammed Ali Kouidri and Nawel taleb	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 75

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
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Y-72	First-principles study of ferromagnetic Half-metallic Electronic structural and elastic properties Electronic, structural and elastic properties Cs ₂ CrGe	Mohammed KESSAS, Samira CHERID, Saadiya BENATMANE, Rachida BENTATA, Zineb FARES, BENTATA Samir and Aissa GUESMIA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 149
Y-73	A new approach allowing the production of electrical energy by advanced oxidation.	Rahma. Benyahia, Ilhem Ghodbane and Saida Zougar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 153
Y-74	Natural acid catalyzed synthesis, in silico study (DFT, ADMET) of some benzoxazolinone schiff based : Interaction with NOS enzyme	Houria BENTOUMI, Aicha AMIRA, Hacen Ktir, Zineb AOUF, Yasmine Chemam, Noureddine AOUF	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 154
Y-75	A review on development of bio-active 2-oxo-1,2-dihydroquinoline derivatives:Recent advances	Ayoub El-mrabet, Youssef Kandri Rodi, Skalli Mohamed Khalid, Amal Haoudi, Ahmed Mazzah	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, France	Submission 155
Y-76	Photocatalytic hydrogen production using TiO ₂ /Pt-graphene without agent of sacrifice	Ricardo López Medina, Bianca Yazmin Alejandre Zúñiga, José Luis Contreras Larios, Elizabeth Rojas García, Ana Marisela Maubert Franco, Marcos May Lozano	Mexico, Mexico, Mexico, Mexico, Mexico, Mexico	Submission 156
Y-77	Psychological effects of coronavirus on reception delinquency in undergraduate students	Amara Sahraoui	Algeria	Submission 157
Y-78	Quantum chemical computational study of intermolecular charge transfer complex formed with Metronidazole and Π acceptor: Conceptual DFT, MESP and QTAIM approaches	Khawla Yahiaoui, Lynda Seridi and Karima Mansouri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 158
Y-79	Thermodynamic Properties of Graphene in Noncommutative geometry	Lakhdar Sek, Mokhtar Falek and Mustafa Mounni	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 91
Y-80	Robustness of the direct speed control of double star induction machine	Basma BENBOUYA, Hocine CHEGHIB	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 58

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Y-81	New Efficient Family of Conjugate Gradient Methods with Strong Wolfe Line Search Conditions	Amina Hallal, Mohammed Belloufi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 163
Y-82	FROM CORK WASTES TO ELECTRICAL THERMAL AND HYDROGEN BIOENERGY	RAFIKA HELAIMIA	Algeria	Submission 4
Y-83	A survey on automated systems for classification of leukocyte for detection of leukemia	Leila Ryma LAZOUNI, Mourtada Benazzouz and Fethallah HADJILA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 166
Y-84	Urolithiasis in Western Algeria	ABBASSENE Fatiha, MESSAOUDI Nadia, BENDAHMANE Leila, BELHADJI Amel Kenza, ADDOU Ahmed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 173
Y-85	Plant community structure and botanical diversity in arid steppe of Algeria (Biskra)	Amina BELHADJ, Fatma DEMNATI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 175
Y-86	Analytical modeling of a reinforced graded sandwich member with GFRP face sheets	Medjmadj Sara, Ait Taleb Souad and Si Salem Abdelmadjid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 176
Y-87	Intelligent Pastoral Ecosystems Monitoring Based AI and Satellite Images	Narimane Benouakta, Belkacem Benadda and Zohra Slimane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 169
Y-88	Assessment of the nutritional quality of four lentils (<i>Lens culinaris</i>) varieties cultivated in Algeria	Djouher GAAD, Salema Silabdi, Abdeslam Belb eldi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 159
Y-89	Anti-obesogenic effect of the aerial parts of <i>Matricaria pubescens</i> in wistar rats fed a high fat diet	Housseem CHENNA, Yahia KHELEF, Chaouki DJOUDER, Imen HALIMI ,Amel BOUMENDJEL and Mahfoud MESSARAH	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 179
Y-90	Removal of organic pollutants from wastewater effluents by combination a sand filter and a planted bed	Khouloud BELHADJ, Leila MILECH and Lynda HECINI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 180

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
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Y-92	On analysis of fractional order mathematical model of Toxoplasmosis using fractal fractional derivative	Medjoudja Meroua, Mohamed Helal, Ahmed Boudaoui, Mohammed el hadi Mezabia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 184
Y-93	Line Voltage Unbalance Factor Degradation by Domestic Single-Phase PV	Youcef BOT, Abdelkader YOUSFI and Ahmed ALLALI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 160
Y-94	Positive periodic solutions to a delay Mackey-Glass model	Marwa Khemis	Algeria	Submission 181
Y-95	Removal of Methyl Blue using new natural clay by applied response surface methodology	Razika Mecheri, Salem Atia, Abd Elkader Ziouani, Ammar Zobeidi, Abd Elkader Benmnin, Oumelkheir Rahim	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 59
Y-96	Contribution to the protection of photovoltaic systems by artificial intelligence techniques	Samira Boumous, Zouhir Boumous, Samia Latrèche, Hamou Nouri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 189
Y-97	Axial and Centrifugal Pumps Design and Optimization Using New Sizing Software	MARAF Salaheddinea , MESSAOUDI Laïd, MEBARKI Ghazali	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 183
Y-98	Geothermal potential of the western part of Ukraine	Taras Popadynets, Sviatoslav Iuras, Denys Panevnyk	Ukraine, Ukraine, Ukraine	Submission 191
Y-99	Using COVID-19 Masks Dataset to Implement Bidirectional LSTM For Facial Emotion Recognition	Salem Tegani, Telli Abdelmoutia	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 193
Y-100	Topological Degree Theory Using Noncompactness Measure in Fractional Limit Problems	Iatime khadidja	Algeria	Submission 196

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
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Y-102	Psychological methods for treating juvenile delinquency sources	Amara Sahraoui	Algeria	Submission 204
Y-103	Vibration Signals Based Fault Diagnosis of Rotary Machinery Using Transfer Learning	Chirag Mongiaa, Deepam Goyalb, Shankar Sehgal	India, India, India	Submission 188
Y-104	Experimental study of a high-performance mortar based on dune sand and marble waste under flexural loading	Fatma Bouzeboudja, Houria Bouzeboudja, Abdelmadjid Si Salem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 199
Y-105	3D modelling and analysis of encased FRP-concrete composite columns under axial compression	Djenad Sonia, Ait Taleb Souad and Si Salem Abdelmadjid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 205
Y-106	Phytochemical study and potential antioxidant activity of the aqueous extract of Hedera algeriensis	Imen Halimi, Lynda Sabrina Ounaceur, Housseem Chenna, Mahfoud Messarah and Amel Boumendjel	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 195
Y-107	Existence and uniqueness of positive periodic solutions for an iterative hematopoiesis model	Marwa Khemis	Algeria	Submission 209
Y-108	3D Numerical Analyses of the Effect of Deep Braced Excavation on Nearby Pile Behavior	Tamir Amari, Mohamed Nabil Houhou	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 210
Y-109	Kinetic study and dissolution of oxalocalcic stones in the presence of Nigella Sativa extract	Leila Bendahmane, Nadia Messaoudi, Fatiha Abbassene, Amel Kenza Belhadji and Ahmed Addou	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 211
Y-110	Design of ZnO-Zn ₂ TiO ₄ supported bimetallic Pd-Ag catalyst for caffeine photodegradation	F.Z. Janani, S. Charafi, N. Taoufik, A. Elhalil, R. Elmoubarki and N. Barka	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 214

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
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Y-112	Predicting the effect of temperature and relative humidity on the mechanical properties of roller compacted concrete pavement (RCCP) using experimental design	Moussa Deghfel, Abdelaziz Meddah, Mohamed Aziz Chikouche, Miloud Beddar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 208
Y-113	Study of Si:C ratio of the electrochemical properties of silicon/carbon based paste anode for Li ion batteries	Bozetine Isma, Abdelhak Cheriet, Chafiaa Yaddadene, Fatima Boudeffar, Aissa Keffous, Ali Mameri and Amar Manseri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 223
Y-114	Saponification of Rosin: Synthesis and Characterization with physicochemical properties	Asma Hennouni, Somia Hammou and Amine Harrane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 220
Y-115	Synthesis and characterization of new pyrochlore solid solutions (1-x) Gd ₂ Sn ₂ O ₇ – x MO (M = Mg or Zn)	Mohamed Douma, Brahim Arfof, El Hossain Chtoun, El Mokhtar Lemdek	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 224
Y-116	Assessment of noncovalent interactions in OLP@Me β -CD inclusion complex: quantitative and qualitative insights from AIM analysis	Karima Mansouri, Lynda Seridi and Khawla Yahiaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 225
Y-117	A Neural Network extension for analytical turning process modelling	Olivér Hornyák	Hungary	Submission 226
Y-118	structural and elastic properties of SrRu ₂ As ₂ under pressure	Missoum RADJAI	Algeria	Submission 231
Y-119	Notch effects on fatigue crack initiation of 7075 Al-Alloy	Mustapha BENACHOUR, Nadja BENACHOUR	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 232
Y-120	Spiropyran/Merocyanine Amphiphile in Various Solvents: Theoretical Approach to Photophysical Properties and Self-Assembly	Vladyslav Savchenko, Olga Guskova	Germany, Germany	Submission 217

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
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Y-122	Removal of an Orange G azo dye on granular activated carbon based on Olive stones	N. Douara, M. Benzekri Benallou, Z. Mekibes, M. Teroul, S. Attouti, B. Bestani, N. Benderdouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 237
Y-123	Removal of a pharmaceutical pollutant by adsorption on calcined synthetic hydrotalcite	Karima DEBBAH, Nadia AIDER	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 238
Y-124	Modeling of the adsorption isotherm of Rhodamine B	N. Douara, M. Benzekri Benallou, Z. Mekibes, B. Bestani, N. Benderdouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 239
Y-125	Physiological and biochemical mechanism study of abscisic acid involvement in the bean (<i>Phaseolus Vulgaris</i> L.) osmotic adjustment, subject to salinity	Hicham BERRABAH, Belgacem NOUAR, Benchohra MAAMAR and Habiba LAHOUEL	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 240
Y-126	The determination of the soil reaction modulus of soil-pipeline interaction system considering soil variability.	Chahrazad Bacha, Meriem Zoutat and Mohamed Mekki	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 248
Y-127	Separation of microparticles using acoustic force	Zahra Taheri, Morteza Bayareh	Iran, Iran	Submission 251
Y-128	Mechanical behaviour of cohesive soils treated with a bio-binder	Nouaouria Abdessalam, Mohamed Salah Nouaouria, Djalel Khechaimia, Tawfiq Ammar Tawfiq Abu Zarifa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 255
Y-129	Assessment of Geological Site Effects Due To 2003 Boumerdes Earthquake	Sonia Outayeb, Samia Louadj and Amar Louzai	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 262
Y-130	Exact controllability of wave equation: description of the Hilbert Uniqueness method	Billal Elhamza, Wissem Chougar and Abdelhak Hafdallah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 268

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
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Y-132	Buckling response of composited foam core sandwich walls: A nonlinear local approach analysis	Ait Taleb Souad, Medjmadj Sara and Si Salem Abdelmadjid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 192
Y-133	Elimination of diclofenac by an Algerian mineral clay	MAAZOUZI Assia, HOUDA Lakhdar, AGUEDAL Hakim and MEROUANI Djilali Redha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 257
Y-134	A geochemical approach for the Study of the genetic correlation between gold and silver in Rudabánya, Hungary	Mohamed Abdelnaby Oraby, Földessy János	Hungary, Egypt	Submission 258
Y-135	2-nitrophenol removal and adsorption using inexpensive carbonaceous materials	Mohamed Khechai, Amir Djellouli, Dhirar Benselm, Linda heceni	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 284
Y-136	Effect of the volume fraction of layers on the free vibration analysis of functionally graded sandwich plates	Bentrar Hakim, Belalia Sid Ahmed and Chorfi Sidi Mohamed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 285
Y-137	TiO ₂ –Nanotube Formation by Two-Step Anodization for Efficient Photocatalytic application	Rima Ben mammam, Lamia Hamadou	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 286
Y-138	EVALUATION OF ANALGESIC ACTIVITY Citrus ESSENCES HARVESTED LOCALLY IN CHLEF (ALGERIA): In vivo STUDY	Amine BENGAG, Fatima Nehal, Saadia Benelhadj Djelloul	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 5
Y-139	On dynamic characteristic performance of FG-CNT reinforced composite beams with temperature-dependent material properties	Iheb Eddine Houalef, Ismail Bensaïd and Ahmed Saimi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 283
Y-140	Mathematical study of some contact problems	Guenoune chahira and Aziza Bachmar	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 228

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-141	Study of the compressive strength of high-performance mortar based on dune sand	Fatma Bouzeboudja, Houria Bouzeboudja, Souad Ait Taleb	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 267
Y-142	Adsorption of a cationic dye on membrane-free eggshells	Atef Ali Ahmed, Zhour Hattab, Yamina Berredjem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 229
Y-143	A comparative study between global and local sensitivity analysis of the overall damping of the Soil-Structure Interaction (SSI) system	zoutat meriem, bousmaha mohammed, Chahrazed Bacha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 269
Y-144	Simulation of marl degradation by accelerated aging cycles in the laboratory	Sabrina Haddad, Bachir Melbouci and Sonia Outayeb	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 306
Y-145	Influence of surface water circulation on the mechanical strength of schist	Sabrina Haddad, Bachir Melbouci and Sonia Outayeb	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 308
Y-146	Comparison of prevention methods of Decarburization of tool steels during heat treatment	Jawhara Marouani, Jawad zahal and Veres zsolc	Hungary, Hungary, Hungary	Submission 310
Y-147	High-strength Magnetic Beads as Efficient and Reusable Adsorbent of Heavy Metals Recovery	Dhirar BEN SALEM, Abdelkader OUKOUAK, Fouzia TOUAHRA, Maria BERNARDO and Nouredine HAMDJ	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Portugal, Tunisia	Submission 312
Y-148	Model prediction of fatigue life with Gamma function	Abdelfetah Moussouni, Nadja BENACHOUR, Mustapha BENACHOUR	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 315
Y-149	Effect of brick manufacturing water content on crack formation (Bensekrane clay)	Amina Tahar Berrabah, Belabaci zyneb, Attou soria, Rahmani Iness, Attia Amina	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 316
Y-150	Effect of water tank presence and positioning on the response spectrum behavior of a building	Amina Tahar Berrabah, Boukli hacen Abdelmalek Abdelhadi, Betaouaf Abderrahim, Attia Amina	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 318

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-151	Modeling the core-skin bond interface of bio-based multilayered sandwiches under axial compression	Si Salem Abdelmadjid, Medjmadj Sara and Ait Taleb Souad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 174
Y-152	Structural and tribological properties of the mechanically alloyed Ni80Cr20 alloy	Anfal Kaddour, Leila Dekhil, Fatima Zohra Derradji and Mohammed Boulkra	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 129
Y-153	High figure of merit in p type sp based half Heusler compound LiSrSi for thermoelectric applications via ab initio calculations	Mohammed Amine Boudjeltia, Zoubir Aziz, Sabria Terkhi, Yasmine Bouladiab	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 202
Y-154	Analysis of fluid rheological properties on fluid viscous dampers behaviour	BOUAYAD AGHA Mohammed El-Mahdi, RAS Abdelouahab and HAMDAOUI Karim	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 227
Y-155	Application method definition of direction of the solution movement and direction to its sources	Oleksandr Kostiuk	Ukraine	Submission 221
Y-156	H-infinity controller and mu synthesis design for Blood Glucose Regulation in Diabetes Patients in the Presence of Uncertain parameters	Hachana aicha, Abdelaziz mourad	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 259
Y-157	RECOVERY OF ORGANIC WASTE FOR WATER DENITRIFICATION	Selma Si smail, ouardia Benbelkacem, Wahiba Lemlikchi, Hachemi Messaoud	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 314
Y-158	First-principle investigation of structural, electronic, and elastic properties of CoN4 monolayer	Hosayn Chibani	Algeria	Submission 317
Y-159	Experimental measurement and modelling of the Ahmed body aerodynamics	Ait Taleb Belkacem and Laced Seddik	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 206
Y-160	Valorization and Characterization of Biomass Ash in Compressed Earth Bricks	Nadia BOUSSAA, Nasser CHELOUAH and Fatma KHELOUI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 313

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-161	Experimental Study on the Shear Strength of Steel Fibres Reinforced High Performance Concrete Beams Without Stirrups	Touhami Tahenni	Algeria	Submission 263
Y-162	The effect of bath temperature on the corrosive behavior of zinc in a saline medium in the presence of ceria nanoparticles	Amira Fadia Ghomrani, Nahla Kadri, Youcef Hamlaoui, Kerroum Derbal	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 101
Y-163	Influence of nanoparticle shape on the magnetohydrodynamic of the copper-water nanofluid flow over a linearly semi-infinite sheet	Manar Ennaouri, El-Kaber Hachem and Zouhair Amraoui	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 327
Y-164	EEG-Based Seizure Detection Using Feed-Forward and LSTM Neural Networks Based on a Neonates Dataset	Amr Zeedan, Khaled Al-Fakhroo and Abdulaziz Barakeh	Qatar, Qatar, Qatar	Submission 351
Y-165	A Rolling Bearing Fault Identification Based on Vibration Signals Analysis Using DWT-DFT technique	Saida DAHMANE, Fouad BERRABAH and Mohamed Razi MORAKCHI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 470
Y-166	Nylosan Red textile dye elimination: Adsorption and RSM evaluation	Amel BELAYACHI-HADDAD, Nouredine BENDERDOUCHE, Benaouda BESTANI and Chérif HADDAD	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 14
Y-167	Physical-mechanical properties of sanitary ceramic bodies contained Algerian blast furnace slag.	Khaled Boulaiche, Hichem Alioui	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 144
Y-168	Internet of Things (IoT) and digital marketing	Georgios Polydoros, Eleni Drakaki	Greece, Greece	Submission 488
Y-169	Social media: customer satisfaction and loyalty	Georgios Polydoros	Greece	Submission 504
Y-170	Simulation and modeling of aluminum cold rolling	M.Kheroufi, M.Zaaf, A.Amirat, W.Ghennai	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 200

Session 3.18		12 NOVEMBER 2022 14:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-53	Development of Semi-Renewable Soft Hydrogels via Photopolymerisation	Fatma Nur PARIN and Uğur PARIN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 16
O-54	Genetic Optimization Application for TMD Position on the Flexible Structure	Mehmet Akif Koç, Mustafa Eroğlu, İsmail Esen	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 260
O-55	Metal Kalkojenit İnce Filmlerin Elektrodepozisyon ile Üretilmesi, Karakterizasyonu, Elektrokatalik ve Elektronik Özelliklerin İncelenmesi	Uğur Gül, Ali Ercan Ekinci, Kemal Volkan Özdokur, Emre Yavuz and Çiğdem Eden	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 732
O-56				

Session 3.19		12 NOVEMBER 2022 17:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-171	The application of engineering psychology and ergonomics in organizations and businesses	Ioannis Chetroi	Greece	Submission 534
Y-172	Recent Developments in Lignocellulosic Sugar Palm Fibre and Their Applications	M. Imraan, R.A. Ilyas, A.S Norfarhana	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 563
Y-173	A simple higher order shear deformation theory for the free vibration of functionally graded plates	Amina Attia, Amina Tahar Berrabah	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 367
Y-174	Numerical Modeling of Turbulent Convective Flow of Humid-Air in a Vertical Duct	Chati Tounsi, Rouibah Abdelkader, Naas Toufik Tayeb, Rahmani Kouider and Telha Mostefa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 323
Y-175	Image reconstruction: applied a sampling uniform mask and random mask to the MRI images	A. Bekki, A. Korti	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 328
Y-176	Degradation of organic matter in the presence of wastewater by a modified oxidation process	Rayene Koliai, Awatef Belghit	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 329
Y-177	Averaged optimal control for parabolic systems depending on parameter	Wissem Chougar, Bilal Elhamza and Abdelhak Hafdhalla	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 330
Y-178	Calculation of pulmonary artery diameter for pulmonary hypertension prediction	K.N. HAKKOUM and L.HAMZA CHERIF	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 342
Y-179	Investigation of the structural, elastic, and electronic properties of Perovskite BaKBr3 Crystal: A First-Principles Study	Sarah Chaba mouna, Missoum Radjai	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 344
Y-180	NiO nanoparticles induce cytotoxicity and oxidative damage in human lung cells (A549)	Mohamed Khiari and Zine Kechrid	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 345

Session 3.20		12 NOVEMBER 2022 18:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-181	Hybrid fractional differential equations with Ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative	Abdelatif Boutiara	Algeria	Submission 348
Y-182	Dam sludge effects - as a cement substitution- on cementitious materials	Mohamed Aziz Chikouche, Laid Baali, Saida Boualleg and Moussa Deghfel	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 350
Y-183	Statistical study of DC breakdown voltage of natural ester compared with mineral oil	Abderrahim Reffas, Abderazak Benna, Oualid Aissa, Hicham Talhaoui, Abderrahmane Beroual, and Hocine Moulai	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 354
Y-184	Ultrasonic Characterization of Mortar	Hana Slimani, Nesrine Cheniti, Kamal Abdelli, Tarek Boutkedjirt	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 356
Y-185	SYNERGISTIC DEGRADATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL XENOBIOTICS USING MICROBIAL COMMUNITIES	Boutheina TRAD, Zidane BRANES	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 360
Y-186	Human finger based multi-biometrics system using WQAM	Abderrahmane Herbadji and Djamel Herbadji	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 362
Y-187	Removal of malachite green from aqueous solutions by adsorption on walnut shells	Leila Mahfoudi, Atef Ali Ahmed, Zhou Hatta	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 363
Y-188	Preparation and characterization of new mesoporous materials of type Co-HMS-n. Study of their catalytic performance in the degradation of a pharmaceutical pollutant in water	DJELLOUDI Thiziri, ZEKRI Ouardia and TOUAHRA Fouzia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 368
Y-189	Comparative study on photocatalytic performance under uv/solar light of ZnO-nanoparticles Synthesized by green method	Mohamed AIT OUMERACI, Tarek BERRAMA, Hayet TIZI, Feriel SAHOUI, Meriem DEHBI, Yassine KADMI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 369
Y-190	Facile and green synthesis of magnesium oxide nanoparticles for the degradation of methylene blue dye under UV irradiation	Mohamed AIT OUMERACI, Tarek BERRAMA, Hayet TIZI, Feriel SAHOUI, Meriem DEHBI, Yassine KADMI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 370

Session 3.21		12 NOVEMBER 2022 18:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-191	Removal of bioremediation micropollutants by adsorption on natural support: Kinetic Study	Ghania BELLIL, Rokaia LAKHDARI, Nedjma KHELIFA, Nadia Aicha LAOUFI, Katia BRIBI and Yasmine LADOUL	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 371
Y-192	Local existence of solution for a nonlinear kirchhoff type reaction diffusion equation with variable exponents	Aya Khaldi, Amar Ououa and Wissem Boughamsa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 375
Y-193	Exponential decay of solution for a class to semilinear wave equation with damping and source terms	Aya Khaldi, Amar Ououa and Wissem Boughamsa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 376
Y-194	On local existence of solution for a class to semilinear hyperbolic equation	Aya Khaldi, Amar Ououa and Wissem Boughamsa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 377
Y-195	Seismic rehabilitation of existing reinforced concrete buildings in Algeria	Nadia Diboune, Berradia Mohammed	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 378
Y-196	Employees' perception and behavior following telework's widespreadness brought by Covid- 19 Crisis	Ensem Mourou, BARTHA Zoltan	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 385
Y-197	Bond Graph Modeling of Electromechanical System	Samia Latreche, Mabrouk Khemliche and Samira Boumous	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 388
Y-198	Hypothyroidism during pregnancy	*DJAARA Hayat, BELHADI Kamilia	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 391
Y-199	Numerical Resolution of a Reaction-Diffusion System by the Finite Element Method in Dimension 2	Chabekh Meriem, Chougui Nadhir	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 393
Y-200	Adaptive Synergetic Projective Synchronization of Hyperchaotic System	Y. Haddadji, M.N. Harmas, O.Gherouat	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 400

Session 3.22		12 NOVEMBER 2022 19:00-20:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-201	Behavior of expansive soil stabilized by natural and artificial stabilizers	Abd elmalik GOUFI	Algeria	Submission 407
Y-202	Phytochemical study, antioxidant activity of EUPHORBIA RESINIFERA L.	Bounoua Nadia, Rebizi Nadjib Med	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 409
Y-203	Microbiological and biochemical identification of potential bacteria potato	Charef Maysoune, OuanasSouheila and Branes Zidane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 414
Y-204	Influence of temperature on the synthesis reaction of heterocyclic compounds type betaine with a pyrimidine ring	Malki Fatiha, Missoum Amina	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 416
Y-205	On the regularity of generalized functions	Mohamed El Amine Kherarba, Mohamed Helal and Amel Bouraada	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 417
Y-206	Artificial Intelligence to Predict the Real Part of the Refractive Index of Hemoglobin	Faiza Omari, Samira Tared, Latifa Khaouane, Maamar Laidi and Abdellah Ibrir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 418
Y-207	Numerical Analysis Of The Effect Of Composite Patch Damage By Cracking On The Repair Performance Of An AL 2024 T3 Structure	Talbi Sofiane, Salem Mokadem, Mechab Belaïd, Baghdadi Mohamed, Allem Ahmed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 420
Y-208	Mechanical behavior of saturated sandy soils under shaking effect	Mohammed BOUSMAHA, Meriem ZOUTAT, Abdelkader HACHICHI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 426
Y-209	New stress-strain relationship for square and rectangular concrete columns confined with CFRP wraps	Nadia Diboune, Riad Benzaid and Mohammed Berradia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 428
Y-210	Existence and uniqueness of the mild solution for parabolic impulsive equation	M. CHAOUCH and Rahima ATMANIA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 430

Session 3.23		12 NOVEMBER 2022 19:00-20:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-211	Speed Control of Two Induction Motors Using a Five Arms DC-AC Inverter	Boukhari Mohamed, Ismail Ghadbane and Bouzidi riad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 433
Y-212	A PROTOTYPE OF AN IOT-BASED SMART OVERLOAD IGNITION CONTROL DEVICE USING ARDUINO	V.Pravin Raj, S.Yuvarajan, R.Sugashini, M.Gnanaprakash and S.P.Mangaiyarkarasi	India, India, India, India, India	Submission 434
Y-213	Study the Temperature Effect and the Porosity on the Propagation Modes Velocities in Porous Ceramics via Acoustic Technique	F. Hamdi	Algeria	Submission 435
Y-214	Computational Analysis of Magnetic fluid flow in a loop	Jaswinder Singh Mehta, Rajesh Kumar, Harmesh Kumar, Harry Garg, Arvinder Mehta	India, India, India, India, India	Submission 437
Y-215	Modeling of Photovoltaic Cell and Module Using PVPyAMS Software	Dhiabi Fathi, Benelmir Okba and Saadoune Achour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 441
Y-216	Impact of curing regime on the kinetics of the physico-mechanical behavior in combined sand (dune and recycled) concrete	Tahar ZERIG, Assia AIDOU, Tarek DJEDID, Abdelhamid KHELIFI, Mouloud BELACHIA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 442
Y-217	In silico docking and ADMET study of curcumin derivatives as potential anti-cancer agents	Narimene Chahbaoui, Saida Khamouli	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 449
Y-218	Influence of different polymers on the characteristics of Algerian bitumen	Mahroug Hanane, Jidoumou Mohamed Mahmoud, Bizimana Believe	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 453
Y-219	Well posedness for a plate equation with non-homogeneous boundary conditions	El-Hadi KAMEL	Algeria	Submission 455
Y-220	Beta tricalcium phosphate composition during bovine bone's heat treatment	Zineb Amraoui, Djamel Belamri	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 456

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P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-221	Nonparametric prediction of kernel regression.	Elhadj HAMEL	Algeria	Submission 458
Y-222	Mechanical and Physical properties of concrete made with rubber tire : A Review	Meryem Adjeroud, Karima Gadri and Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 459
Y-223	Contribution to the study of the fresh and hardened state behaviour of self-compacting concrete based on calcined silt of Brezina dam	Sallai Hind Hidayet, Bouhamou Nasrdine and Maarouf Hafida, Belghit Abdelkadir, Jalal Boussebiate, Torki Flio	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 460
Y-224	Synthesis of PANI@ZnO Hybrid Material: Structural Characterization and Adsorption Performance	I.Toumi, A. Benyoucef	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 464
Y-225	Synthesis and Characterization of Polymer Nanocomposites with Inorganic Filler for Textile Applications	I.Toumi, A. Benyoucef	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 465
Y-226	Poisson Lindley modified process	Grine Razika	Algeria	Submission 481
Y-227	Intelligent liquid level control for a coupled two-tank system by using an adaptive fuzzy logic controller	Mohammed Amin Benmahdjoub, Youcef Saidi and Meddah Atallah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 491
Y-228	A Theoretical study of molecular docking of some aminophosphonates: In Silico study "New Inhibitors of the Coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 Protease"	Nour el houda Felkaoui, Abdelkader Hellal	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 492
Y-229	ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY AND TOTAL PHENOLIC CONTENT OF Salvia SPECIES.	FELKAOUI NourELHouda, KABOUCHE Ahmed, KABOUCHE Zahia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 496
Y-230	Synthesis and biological activity of an antibiotic: New fluoroquinolone derivative; N-substituted ciprofloxacin-C7-piperazine.	Nour ELHoud Felkaoui, Mostefa Mokhenane	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 499

Session 3.25		12 NOVEMBER 2022 20:00-21:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-231	Position control of a permanent magnet stepper motors by using conventional and intelligent controllers	Mohammed Amin Benmahdjoub, Youcef Saidi and Meddah Atallah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 501
Y-232	The Contribution of ANN for the predicting of the missing well logs data.	Khalda ZABEL, Berguig Mohamed Cherif and Ketteb Rachid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 502
Y-233	STUDY AND PHYSICO-MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF POLY V TRANSMISSIONBELTS	S. Mahseur, S. Lecheb, H. Kebir, B. Bezzazi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 505
Y-234	Prediction of Hepatitis Prognosis Using Multilayer Perceptron	Samira Tared, Faiza Omari, Mohamed Roubehie Fissa, Latifa Khaouane, and Salah Hanani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 509
Y-235	Recognition of Face Image in Kernal Space Using Machine Learning	Berrimi Fella and Hedli Riadh	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 522
Y-236	A Novel Investigation of Power Allocation Scheme Based on Zipf Distribution for NOMA Systems	Himeur Hanane, Meriah Sidi Mohammed and Derraz Fouad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 526
Y-237	Existence of distributional solution for fractional partial differential system	Chaima Saadi, Hakim Lakhal, Esma Abada and Nadjla Abidat	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 533
Y-238	Fault diagnosis method of spur gear based on CEEMDAN and Neural Networks	Kamar ZAIEM, Hichem BOURAS and Mohamed Faouzi RACHEDI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 546
Y-239	Experimental study on corrosion effect on mechanical properties of API 5L X70 steel	Mounira Derfoul, Samira Tlili, Abdelkader Khetache, Mohamed Hassani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 550
Y-240	Analysis of the MPPT INC algorithm using variable irradiation	Rahli Chouaib, Ouada Mehdi and Saad Salah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 553

Session 3.26		12 NOVEMBER 2022 21:00-22:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-241	Characterization of the mineral composition of the clay of the Soubella region and the bentonite of Mighnia	Karima Larkat, Azzedine Benyahia, Meftah Allal, Nadir Deghfel, Nedjma lahmar, Issam Belfar, Brahim Ben Saoucha.	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 562
Y-242	Second order sliding mode control of a wind energy conversion system based on a double fed asynchronous machine	Labib Bensaadia, Riyadh Rouabhi, Djaleddine Khodja and Abdelghafour Herizi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 566
Y-243	Review on Lignocellulosic Bamboo Fibers as Papermaking Material: Properties And Applications	Lim Joe Yee Jessica, R.A. Ilyas and Nur Hafizah Ab Hamid	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 572
Y-244	Structural and electronic properties of the cubic perovskite BaZrO ₃ : DFT calculations	Ouahiba Ramdane, Malika Labidi, Salima Labidi and Rachid Masrour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Morocco	Submission 574
Y-245	COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN OIL WELL SAND CONCRETE REINFORCED WITH FIBRES AND SAND CONCRETE CONTAINING PNEUMATIC WASTE	Khelaifa Ammar, Mani Mohammed and Logbi Abdelaziz	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 575
Y-246	POLYPHENOLIC PROFILE AND LARVISCIDAL EFFECT OF AERIAL PARTS OF LINUM SPECIES	CHEBCHOUB Soumya, KABOUCHE Zahia	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 577
Y-247	Improving the Performance of PV Panels by Cooling Mechanism based on Air Conditioning	Toufik Sebbagh, Salim Alidra and Lamia Benzaid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 579
Y-248	3D elastic analysis simulation of direct simple shear tests shearing	Chehat Azeddine, Merabti Salem and Boudina Abde-Allah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 582
Y-249	A comparative experiment of cement materials' characteristics composite from expanded and raw cork granules waste	Merabti.Salem, Boudina Abdellah	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 583
Y-250	The Evaluation Of The Antioxidant Activity And The Valorization Of The Genus Rubus Ulmifolius	RAHMOUN Asma, GHANEMI Fatima Zohra, MAMOUN Chaima, BENARBIA Kaddour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 590

Session 3.27		12 NOVEMBER 2022 21:00-22:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-251	Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) measurement, data processing and modelling to estimate the electromagnetic (EM) parameters of the investigated media	Khouloud Jlaiel, Endre Nádas	Hungary, Hungary	Submission 599
Y-252	Intraperitoneal injection of cigarette smoke extract induce COPD lung inflammation in mice	Nada SLAMA, Karima BAHRIA, Amina ABDELLATIF, Mustapha OUMOUNA, George BIRKMYAR and Karine BENACHOUR	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 607
Y-253	In Situ Hemi-synthesis of imines using Perillaldehyde from Ammodaucus leucotrichus subsp leucotrichus	Ramzi Maadadi, Abbes Benmerache, Zahia Kabouche and Khaldoun Bachari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 610
Y-254	Effect of waste tyre rubber on mechanical properties of cement mortar	Hamad Khelaifa, Laid Bedadi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 611
Y-255	Experimental Validation of Efficient DFIG-Variable Speed Wind Turbine Control based on stand-alone Mode	Fayssal AMRANE	Algeria	Submission 614
Y-256	Robust Adaptive Power Control for Doubly Fed induction Generator under a Fixed Switching Frequency	Fayssal AMRANE	Algeria	Submission 615
Y-257	Advanced Signal Processing Technique for Ball Bearing Fault	Yahia Bouseloub, Farida Medjani, Ali Belhamra and Tahar Kezai	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 616
Y-258	Interference study of an electrochemical sensor based on Heteropolyanion of Dawson type for detection of m-cresol	Rim Lamari, Saida Zougar, Kheireddine Bouzid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 617
Y-259	Mechanical behavior of sand concrete	Oday Jaradat, Karima Gadri, Asal Sirhan and Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 621
Y-260	Investigation of an All-steel buckling restrained brace with auxetic core under cyclic loads	Hamza Basri, Ras Abdelouahab and Karim Hamdaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 624

Session 3.30		12 NOVEMBER 2022 14:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
O-64	Supercapacitor Application of rGO/NiO/PANI electrodes for 2032 coin cell and SS electrodes	Murat Ateş	Turkey	Submission 868
O-65	Synthesis of rGO/CuO/PANI nanocomposite for Supercapacitor evaluations	Murat Ateş	Turkey	Submission 834
O-66	Comparison of electrolyte effects for rGO/Fe ₂ O ₃ /PANI nanocomposites	Murat Ateş	Turkey	Submission 861
O-67	Kenevir/Pamuk Karışımı Kumaşların UV Destekli Hidrofilleştirilmesi	Semiha Eren, Buket Mecir, İdil Yiğit and Ozan Avin	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 751

Session 3.28		12 NOVEMBER 2022 22:00-23:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-261	Chitin and Chitosan Based Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment	Chew Yee Yung, Mohamad Fazrul Rizal, Najihah Suriana, Chung Jing Yi and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 626
Y-262	Lignin Based Materials for Sustainable Treatment	Lim Hong Xu, Muhamad Alif Syahmi Muhamad Yacob, Nurul Nabihah Binti Zulkifli and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 627
Y-263	On the separation of complex modes for the non-classically damped systems	Hisham Suleiman, Mahdi Abdeddam and Hamid Afra	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 629
Y-264	Cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) Based Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment	Oo Yong Jie, Awadh Salem, Nabilla Wahyu Hasanah, Fatin Nursyahraien Mohd Fauzi and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 630
Y-265	Natural Fibre Based Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment	Muhammad Alif Aiman Ramli, Mohammed Ahmed Albatati, Fatin Nur Hidayah Mohd Zaile, Ling Bei En and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 631
Y-266	Cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) based materials for sustainable water treatment	Chee Shu Yi, Victoria Sharon Vincent Jillson, Souleymane Djibrine Abdelrassoul, Arif Hashri Aminnordin and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 632
Y-267	Pectin Based Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment	Ebrahim Abdo Mohammad Gaber, Aurelia Salwa Naratya Putri, Lim Shi Xin, Ahmad Zakwan Anuar and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 633
Y-268	Starch Based Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment	Alam Surya Putrawan, Asvenna Loduni, Puteri Elisa Sabrina Fadzil, Vivien Teo Jia Wen, Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 634
Y-269	Alginate Based Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment	Omar Mohammed Ali Albaagari, Muhammad Akmal Arif Mohd Akta, Siti Farah Inani Zulkifly, Stah Ling Li and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 635
Y-270	Polyethyleneimine Based Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment	Muhammad Farid Wajdi Muhamad Roslan, Mohamed Sherif Mohamed Mamdouh Ibrahim Barakat, Nur Farisya Jamal Abdul Nasir, Tang Jie Xian and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 636

Session 3.29		12 NOVEMBER 2022 22:00-23:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-271	Thermal numerical study of a power transformer in order to improve its cooling	Abderazak. BENNIA, Abderrahim REFFAS, Mohammed Abdul Hameed Khan, Akram BELOUAR and Hachimi FELLOUAH	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 273
Y-272	Biobased Hydrogels for Sustainable Water Treatment	Alif Aiman, Jau Sh Wei, Ahmad Yousef, Nurul Anis and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 637
Y-273	Algae Based Material for Sustainable Wastewater Treatment	Ahmad Rushaidi Ahmad Raif, Md Zaki Wasit Dewan, Lian Jeat Ping, and Subathra A/P Nilamegan and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 638
Y-274	Cellulose Based Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment	Abdelrahman Mohamed Mahmoud Mohamed, Fathima Shiyaza Shariffdeen, Herwin Kuan, Nurul Nasuha Binti Mohd Yusof and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 639
Y-275	Polylactic Acid-Based Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment	Azad Zuhri, Musyazrina Alya, Shamimimraphay, Tham Yu Xiang and Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 640
Y-276	Gum-Based Material for Sustainable Water Treatment	Mohammed Salem Salah Ba Bakr, Felvie Valerie Leong, Vica Aqilla Salwa, Muhammad Zuhilmi, Rushdan Ahmad Ilyas	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 642
Y-277	Detection of Multidrug Resistant Klebsiella in Poultry Meat	Feryal BELFIHADJ, Anfal KARA, Meriem ELKOLLI and Naouel BOUSSUALIM	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 648
Y-278	PEM fuel cell Diagnosis using Convolutional Neural Networks	Hichem Kahia, Saadi Aicha, Abderrahmane Herbadji and Djamel Herbadji	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 649
Y-279	Existence and uniqueness of weak solution results for a nonlinear fractional Laplacian system	Esma Abada, Hakim Lakhal, Chaima Saadi and Nadjla Abidat	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 660
Y-280	Study of the behavior of a mixture of marl and industrial glass debris in compaction tests	Nassima FERRI, Omar BOUDLAL and Mohammed KHATTAOUI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 662

Session 4.1		13 NOVEMBER 2022 09:00-10:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-281	Convolutional neural network for epilepsy detection	G. Chekhmane, R. Benali	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 664
Y-282	Behavior of the marl-industrial glass mixture in the shear test	Nassima FERRI, Omar BOUDLAL and Mohammed KHATTAOUI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 665
Y-283	Study of the behavior of a mixture of marl and industrial glass debris in California Bearing Ratio tests.	Nassima FERRI, Omar BOUDLAL and Mohammed KHATTAOUI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 667
Y-284	Design and performance evaluation of Lab-Scale Solar Dryer for Banana	Junaid Ramzan, Ali Hussain	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 675
Y-285	New result on a new class of sublinear fractional Schrödinger-Maxwell system	Hamza Boutebba	Algeria	Submission 682
Y-286	An extensive review of solar collector for drying application; A smart cities concept	Muhammad Zeeshan, Hammad Ali Qureshi, Asad Ullah and Muhammad Usman Haider	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 684
Y-287	4-Nitrophenol Removal by electrocoagulation	Lynda Hecini, Abdelkader Ouakouak, Fedia Bekiri, Wahida Kherifi, Khechai Mohammed, Nora Bouchahem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 687
Y-288	Power system analysis and improvement with power system stabilizer PSS	Wissam Mouilid, Abdelhalim Telemçani and Karim Sebaa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 697
Y-289	Simulation methodology for artificial accelerograms compatible with target spectra: application to the Boumerdes earthquake of May 21, 2003.	Boudina Abdellah, Chehat Azeddine and Merabti Salem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 704
Y-290	The spectroscopic characterization of the new synthesized heterocyclic aromatic organic compound	Fatima Zohra Boudjenane, Nassima Bourahla, Abdelkader Chouaih and Nouredine Boukabcha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 705

Session 4.2		13 NOVEMBER 2022 09:00-10:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-291	Effect of gypsum on the water holding capacity grounds in the arid regions	Hiouani Fatima1, Aissaoui Hichem	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 39
Y-292	Ni/Al hydrolatcites and their performance in the adsorptive removal of the dye Eriochrome Black T.	Samira Charafi, Fatima Zahra Janani and Alaâeddine Elhalil	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 709
Y-293	Automate Link Specifications Process in Linked Data	Khayra BENCHERIF and Badia KLOUCHE	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 733
Y-294	Study of the Structural, Electronic, and Optical properties of the cubic perovskite CaSnO3 from first principles	Sawsen BELBAHI, Salima LABIDI, Malika LABIDI, Rachid MASROUR	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Morocco	Submission 738
Y-295	3D Investigation of the applied element method (AEM) in the two-dimensional study of concrete beams.	Chehat Azeddine, Boudina Abdellah and Bouaricha Leyla	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 741
Y-296	Hopf bifurcation of TB model with two delay time.	Nadjla Abidat, Esmâ Abada and Chaima Saadi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 752
Y-297	The Influence Of Binder Layers On Pavement Behavior	GUENDOUD Malika, MELBOUCI Bachir and BENLALA A/Hafid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 755
Y-298	Experimental study of the geotechnical properties of the sediments of the Beni Bahdel dam - Wilaya of Tlemcen	Klouche Faiza, Belhouari Fethi, Guiz Amine and Maliki Mustapha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 756
Y-299	Investigation and repurposing of some antifungal drugs for potential inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 main protease.	MERIR Roufaida, BAITICHE Milad, DJERBOUA Ferhat, BOUTAHALA Mokhtar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 772
Y-300	Investigation and repurposing of some antifungal drugs for potential inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 main protease.	MERIR Roufaida, BAITICHE Milad, DJERBOUA Ferhat, BOUTAHALA Mokhtar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 772

Session 4.3		13 NOVEMBER 2022 10:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-301	Characterization of mortars based on local cement materials	Kiboub Mohammed Ycine, Malab Souad, Belaidi Akram Salah, Takhi Kaouthar4	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 779
Y-302	Development of a model generator for mobil-racks AS/RS simulation	Amine Hakim GUEZZEN	Algeria	Submission 798
Y-303	Valorization of waste glass as replacement of sand in cement mortar	Mohamed Amin BOUZIDI, MEZIANI Belkacem	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 799
Y-304	Petrophysical study, monitoring, and evaluation of dolomitization in a carbonate reservoir	Khouloud Jlaiel, Riadh Ahmadi and Farhat Rekhis	Tunusia, Tunusia, Tunusia	Submission 809
Y-305	Study of magnetic properties and magnetocaloric effect of compound NdSi	Rachid Masrour	Morocco	Submission 811
Y-306	Fault-Tolerant Control Schemes Applied to a PMSM Drive System under IGBT Open-Circuit Faults	Hicham Zaimen, Ali Rezig, Said Touati	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 812
Y-307	Microstructure and structural properties of superconducting ceramics Bi ₂ Sr ₂ CaCu ₂ LaxO _{8-δ}	Fatima Harma, Karima Belakroum and Soumia Ramdani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 813
Y-308	Study of THE INCORPORATION OF INORGANIC STRENGTH ON THE STRUCTURAL, MECHANICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF HIGH-DENSITY POLYETHYLENE	BENAYACHE Walid	Algeria	Submission 818
Y-309	Second order sliding mod control of a unifiedpower flow controller using sliding mode control	Abdellatif hinda, Yousfi Abdelkader, Bot youcef	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 824
Y-310	Speed Control of Two Induction Motors Using a Five Arms DC-AC Inverter	Boukhari Mohamed, Ismail Ghadbane and Bouzidi riad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 844

Session 4.4		13 NOVEMBER 2022 10:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-311	Enhanced performance of photocatalytic treatment of wastewater by doped TiO ₂	Abd Errahmane ZEMOURI and Embarek BENTOUHAMI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 851
Y-312	Preparation of TiO ₂ nanotube-based photocatalysts and degradation kinetics of an antibiotic from the pharmaceutical industry	Abd Errahmane ZEMOURI and Embarek BENTOUHAMI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 852
Y-313	Fuzzy Controller of Three Phases Induction Motor Drives under Eccentricity Fault	Rouaibia red*, Dgeghder Yacine and Moussaoui Lotfi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 855
Y-314	Effect of the orientation of the blades on the behavior of a flow around a blade of a steam turbine	Merouane Habib	Algeria	Submission 856
Y-315	Evaporation Cooling System for Greenhouse	Muhammad Adil, Muhammad Sultan	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 862
Y-316	Electrical diagnosis of TIG welding process	S.Benharat, L.Belgacem and D.Doufene	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 871
Y-317	The Investigation of Internal factors in the Precipitator Point-to-Plan Configuration	N.Hebbar, M.Aissou and H.Ait said	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 877
Y-318	Use of Local Materials and Recovered Wastes in the Concrete	Amar Mezidi, Ratiba Mitiche Kettab	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 878
Y-319	Design and performance analysis of Visible Light Communication system through simulation	ABDELMOULA Ahmed, SEKKIOU Imene, BENOUDNINE hadjira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 879
Y-320	Visible light communication: applications, architecture, standardization and research challenges	ABDELMOULA Ahmed, SEKKIOU Imene, BENOUDNINE hadjira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 880

Session 4.5		13 NOVEMBER 2022 11:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-321	An Experimental Study on Visible Light Communication in Biomedical Signal Transmission	ABDELMOULA Ahmed, L'ANTRI Ibrahim, SEKKIOU Imene BENOUDNINE hadjira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 881
Y-322	Implementation of a Solar cell Receiver System for Visible Light Communication	ABDELMOULA Ahmed, L'ANTRI Ibrahim, SEKKIOU Imene BENOUDNINE hadjira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 882
Y-323	PC to PC data transmission using visible light communication	ABDELMOULA Ahmed, L'ANTRI Ibrahim, SEKKIOU Imene BENOUDNINE hadjira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 883
Y-324	AUDIO TRANSMISSION USING VISIBLE LIGHT COMMUNICATION (VLC)	ABDELMOULA Ahmed, SEKKIOU Imene, BENOUDNINE hadjira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 884
Y-325	Exponential Growth of Positive Initial Energy Solutions For Coupled Nonlinear Klein-Gordon Equations With Degenerate Damping and Source Terms	Wissem Boughamsa, Aya Khaldi and Ouaoua Amar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 541
Y-326	Local existence of a nonlinear Timoshenko equation with damping and source terms	Wissem Boughamsa, Aya Khaldi and Ouaoua Amar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 538
Y-327	The Investigation of Internal factors in the Precipitator Point-to-Plan Configuration	N.Hebbar, M.Aissou and H.Ait said	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 19
Y-328	Solitary wave solutions for the conformable fractional coupled nonlinear Schrödinger equations with variable coefficients	Riadh Hedli and Fella Berrimi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 558
Y-329	Protection of the right to property as a constitutional right	Kastriote Vlahna, Hajredin Kuçi	Kosovo, Kosovo	mail submission 20
Y-330	Reasons for conflict of laws	Hajredin Kuçi, Kastriote Vlahna	Kosovo, Kosovo	mail submission 21

Session 4.6		13 NOVEMBER 2022 11:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-331	Importance of Arbitration Law	Argona KUÇI	USA	mail submission 22
Y-332	The foreign element and the ways of its presentation	Argona KUÇI	USA	mail submission 23
Y-333	Public revenues and their importance	Dafina Vlahna	Kosovo, Kosovo	mail submission 24
Y-334	Financing of the state budget for the year 2023-2024	Dafina Vlahna	Kosovo, Kosovo	mail submission 25
Y-335	Comparison between the different types of grape molasses in Algeria by physico-chemical parameter	S. Cherigui, I. Chikhi, H F. Dergal	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 489
Y-336	Structural, electronic and optical properties of CoZrMnIn Half-metallic ferromagnetic Half-Heusler Alloy: A First-Principles study	Khadhraoui Zakaria, Amara Abdelaziz and Salima Labidi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 805
Y-337	A Numerical Study of Reinforced Unpaved Roads	Mohamed Saddek Remadna, Cheima Bouraoui and Mohamed El Hadi Zobiri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 623
Y-338	Efficacious anti-fungal drug repurposing in the development of anticancer agents (In silico molecular docking studies)	MERIR Roufaida, BAITICHE Milad, DJERBOUA Ferhat, BOUTAHALA Mokhtar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 392
Y-339	Valorization of waste of jute fabric and polypropylene as constituents of bio-composites	Mekideche Salih, Rahmouni Zineelabidine and Rokbi Mansour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 666
Y-340	Adomian decomposition method for solving two-component population balance equation for simultaneous growth and aggregation	Khaled Athmani, Abdelmalek Hasseine	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 619

Session 4.7		13 NOVEMBER 2022 12:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-341	Structural and optical properties of ZnO thin layer prepared by sol-gel Spin Coating method	Yousfi Asma, Chorfa Abdellah	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 739
Y-342	Development of an electrochemical sensor based on conductive organic polymer/carbon nanotubes nanocomposite for the detection of a biological molecule	SMANI Dounia and MAOUCHE Naima	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 766
Y-343	Effect of Gamma Irradiation on the Kinetics and Extraction Yield of Rosmarinus Officinalis Essential Oil	Feriel SAHOUI, Tarek Ibn Ziad BERRAMA, Mohamed AIT OUMERACI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 389
Y-344	Structural, electronic, magnetic and elastic properties of perovskite type oxides PuNiO ₃	Cheyma Boualleg, Athmane Meddour	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 527
Y-345	Medical Image Segmentation Based on Discriminant Analysis	Berrimi Fella and Hedli Riadh	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 521
Y-346	Optimization of the Performance of a Concentrated Solar Power Plant, Fresnel Mirror	Fatah Boufoudi, Sofiane Mihoub and Maroua Ferhat	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 564
Y-347	Study effect of metal work function on metal/ β -Ga ₂ O ₃ Schottky photodiodes by Silvaco-Atlas software	Rima cherroun, Afak Meftah, Madani Labed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 406
Y-348	Mathematical optimization of a workshop layout on several rows	OUHOUD Amina, DJERBOUA Wafaa and Taibi Amani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 767
Y-349	Study of the Mechanical Properties of Reactive Powder Concrete at High Temperature	Mounira Chadli, Sara Rais	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 678
Y-350	Phenylketonuria: epidemiological survey and analytical study in Algerian population	boudoukha chahra, Neggache Fateh	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 383

Session 4.8		13 NOVEMBER 2022 12:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-351	Control And Comparison Between Multilevel Inverters Topologies	Hakim KADRI, Abdelhalim TLEMÇANI, Nouredine HENINI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 770
Y-352	Numerical Analysis of The Shear Behavior Of Short Concrete Corbels Reinforced By Several External Reinforcement Techniques	Hiba Zaioune, Samy Mezhoud	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 544
Y-353	Modeling, Simulation and Analysis of efficiency on Threshold Voltage, leakage current, and DIBL: Application to very High-K Material TiO2 Based on short channel FinFET transistor	Bourahla Nassima, Boudjenane Fatima zohra, Megdoud Yousra and Achour Abderraouf	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 423
Y-354	Design And Simulink Implementation Of IPT-Based Wireless Power Transfer Charger For Electric Vehicle	Abdelmoumin HAMRANI, Abdelhalim TLEMÇANI, Said BARKAT	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 592
Y-355	Terminal Sliding mode control for MPPT requirements	Ziyad Bouchama, Nadjat Zerroug and Khalissa Behih	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 672
Y-356	A deep learning based trust- and tag-aware recommender system for e-learning environment	Sara Gasmi, Tahar Bouhadada	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 804
Y-357	Existence results for a delay differential equation with iterative source term	Lynda Mezghiche, Rabah Khemis and Ahlème Bouakkaz	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 462
Y-358	Effect of irregular layers on the dynamic soil response using the Thin-layer method with the perturbation technique	Yassine Abbas, Rachid Djebien, Sidali Denine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 568
Y-359	A deep learning based trust- and tag-aware recommender system for e-learning environment	Sara Gasmi, Tahar Bouhadada	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 804
Y-360	Characterization of mesoporous silica nanocapsules elaborated by Sol-Gel process	Rayenne Latoui, Djallel Bouzid	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 380